

Greater than the Sum of its Parts – Aggregated Wuhan COVID-19 case data points to the wrong side of the Yangtze River

Discrepancies between official epidemiological data from the Chinese National Health Commission/World Health Organization’s COVID-19 origins report and other published studies are dichotomous, with highly significant consequences for the SARS-CoV-2 origin investigation

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“In the case of all things which have several parts and in which the totality is not, as it were, a mere heap, but the whole is something besides the parts, there is a cause....”¹

-Aristotle, *Metaphysics* VIII, 1045a. 8-10

Graphical Abstract

¹ The numerical changes in district case totals for 5 relevant city districts in Wuhan, showing a significant shift in net totals for each side of the Yangtze River; specifically, the results show a **drop** in cases on the West [Huanan Market] side [highlighted in red] and an **increase** in the two Eastern districts where the WIV HQ and its BSL-4 lab complex are located [highlighted in green].

¹ Aristotle, *Metaphysics* Book VIII, section 1045a (translated by Hugh Tredennick), from the Perseus Catalog of Tufts University.
<https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.01.0052%3Abook%3D8%3Asection%3D1045a>

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Abstract

More than 3 years have passed by since the COVID-19 pandemic was sparked by an outbreak of the SARS-CoV-2 virus in the city of Wuhan, China sometime in late 2019; despite the scientific and geopolitical importance of understanding how the pandemic began, the question remains unanswered, in stark contrast to the earlier SARS & MERS outbreaks. Most of the focus in the origin debate has been centered upon the Huanan Seafood Market in Jiangnan District, where the earliest known major cluster of cases emerged in early December 2020. As a result, a vast amount of published epidemiological research has been ignored and an inordinate amount of attention and weight has been given to the pre-2020 set of 174 COVID-19 cases described within the China Annex² of the World Health Organization’s origin report published on March 31st, 2021. A careful analysis of the extant literature shows that the “official” final case statistics differ in their geospatial distribution by approximately 10,710 – a massive shift that artificially exaggerated the Huanan Market side of the Yangtze River, which separates the western side of Wuhan from the east, where the Wuhan Institute of Virology resides.

2 A depiction of the relevant district from both sides of the Yangtze River, along with the general locations of the Huanan Market, WIV and the WIV's BSL-4 laboratory.

² WHO, "WHO-convened Global Study of the Origins of SARS-CoV-2 [China Part]", WHO (3/30/2021). <https://www.who.int/health-topics/coronavirus/origins-of-the-virus>

Introduction

The origin of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, the pathogen responsible for the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic that has infected 676,609,955 people and killed 6,881,955³ since December 2019, continues to be the focus of intense scrutiny and debate. The lack of progress in the effort to uncover the mechanism by which the virus jumped from its likely natural reservoir (horseshoe bats) is striking, given the historically unprecedented volume of scientific research published in the three years since the first warning emerged from the city of Wuhan on December 30, 2019.⁴ As of 5/1/2023, the search term “epidemiology” returns 15,679 results on PubMed’s LitCovid repository,⁵ but arguments about the origin of the pandemic to date have been solely based upon interpretations of a small data set whose veracity is questioned by both scientists who argue in support of a zoonotic origin⁶ for the virus *and* those who argue in favor of a lab-origin.^{7 8}

The purpose of this paper is to highlight the current state of research on the subject, *because in truth, there is a very substantial body of evidence that exists beyond the WHO’s origin report – evidence that undermines the zoonotic (natural) explanation for the sudden appearance of the SARS-CoV-2 virus in a Chinese city the size of Los Angeles.* The lack of *public* awareness about the extant research isn’t surprising, given the incredible impact of the pandemic upon virtually every aspect of daily life, social interaction, economic activity and geopolitical affairs; the lack of *scientific* attention, however, is *stunning*, because the evidence has been ignored by the two groups most directly implicated in any non-natural explanation for the pandemic – the *Chinese scientists* of the Wuhan Institute of Virology

³ [COVID-19 Map - Johns Hopkins Coronavirus Resource Center](#) [as of 4/21/2023; JHU stopped collecting data for the tracker on 3/10/2023].

⁴ Sina Finance [machine translation], “Undiagnosed Pneumonia - China (Hubei): Request for Information”, *ProMed - International Society for Infectious Diseases* (12/30/2019). <https://promedmail.org/promed-post/?id=20191230.6864153>

⁵ [LitCovid - NCBI - NLM - NIH](#) [as of 5/1/2023].

⁶ Michael Worobey, “Dissecting the early COVID-19 cases in Wuhan”, *Science* (11/18/2021). <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.abm4454>

⁷ Alex Washburne *et al.*, “Statistical challenges for inferring multiple SARS-CoV-2 spillovers with early outbreak phylodynamics,” *bioRxiv* (10/13/2022). <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2022.10.10.511625v1.full.pdf>

⁸ Bob Kadlec, Bob Foster & 117th GOP HELP Committee Staff, “Muddy Waters: The Origin of COVID-19 Report – Executive Summary,” Muddy Waters Group (4/17/2023). <https://www.marshall.senate.gov/wp-content/uploads/MWG-EXECUTIVE-SUMMARY-4.17-Final-Version.pdf>

[WIV] [and the 17 representatives who served as national counterparts for the World Health Organization's [WHO] investigation],^{9,10} and the *global virology community* which has rallied overwhelmingly to the defense of its members that were involved in coronavirus research with the WIV. The former group has sought to divert attention away from the city of Wuhan altogether,¹¹ while the latter group has tried to prove that one or more¹² zoonotic transfers occurred at the Huanan Market in Jiangnan District.¹³ Both groups have ignored any evidence which might support differing conclusions; the parsimonious reason, of course, is that the weight of evidence supports the conclusion that those parties have largely absolved themselves of.

The main conclusions:

- The aggregated epidemiological data depicts a geospatial distribution that is incongruent with official Chinese data, dramatically reducing the number of cases from the WIV side of the river while simultaneously increasing the number of cases on the Huanan Market side.
- Virtually **ALL** of the net change between the two sides of the river can be explained on the one hand by subtractions from the 3 districts containing and surrounding the Huanan Market [Jiangnan, Jiang'an and Qiaokou] and the two districts containing the WIV's primary location and the WIV's BSL-4 laboratory [Wuchang and Jiangxia].
- All of the data included within this analysis comes from peer-reviewed, censor-approved sources. 100% of the studies are by Chinese authors, and 82% of them are written by doctors and/or scientists from medical or research institutions within Wuhan itself.

⁹ WHO, "WHO-convened Global Study of the Origins of SARS-CoV-2 [China Part]", *WHO* (3/30/2021).

<https://www.who.int/health-topics/coronavirus/origins-of-the-virus>

¹⁰ WHO, "WHO-convened Global Study of the Origins of SARS-CoV-2 [Annexes]", *WHO* (3/31/2021).

<https://www.who.int/health-topics/coronavirus/origins-of-the-virus>

¹¹ George Gao *et al.*, "Surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 in the environment and animal samples of the Huanan Seafood Market | Research Square", *Research Square* (2/25/2022). <https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-1370392/v1>

¹² Pekar *et al.*, "The molecular epidemiology of multiple zoonotic origins of SARS-CoV-2 | Science", *Science* (7/26/2022).

<https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.abp8337>

¹³ Michael Worobey *et al.*, "The Huanan Seafood Wholesale Market in Wuhan was the early epicenter of the COVID-19 pandemic", *Science* (7/26/2022). <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.abp8715>

It is statistically improbable that any minor errors within this combined set of data can overturn the primary conclusions listed above; at a minimum, the large *net increase* in cases on the Eastern side of the Yangtze River is evidence of an intentional shift of cases away from the Wuhan Institute of Virology *or* evidence of a much larger true number of cases in Wuhan overall. However, the simultaneous *net reduction* of cases in the vicinity of the Huanan Market [the Hankou districts] indicates that the latter situation can't account for all of the discrepancies that currently exists.

As this author wrote two years ago at the start of this project:

“If the epicenter of the early outbreak was not in Jiangnan District [i.e. near the Huanan Market], but in Wuchang District [on the opposite side of the Yangtze River], it would prove that the limited data China released to the WHO was fabricated; more importantly, however, the incredible effort necessary to fabricate a narrative centered on the opposite side of a mile-wide river would inevitably force the world to confront the *real* question of the Wuhan COVID-19 outbreak - *what's in Wuchang that's worth the effort?*”¹⁴

Methods

This analysis is the ultimate product of a more general effort to obtain clarity about where the SARS-CoV-2 virus originally came from and the circumstances that led to its emergence in the city of Wuhan in the fall of 2019; the author sought to shed light upon a subset of evidence which has remained largely unexplored, whether by supporters of zoonosis or a lab-origin or other members of the independent collection of researchers and scientists known as DRASTIC. A significant amount of attention has been focused upon the 174 ‘early cases’ depicted within the WHO’s origin report, but the results of this analysis should rightfully call into question the wisdom of placing too much weight upon a set of data that was provided without supporting documentation – by a set of authors with clear motivation to produce a report that would not implicate their government in the creation or release of a virus which has since caused a global pandemic.

¹⁴ Charles Rixey, "Wuhan's House of Cards: the outbreak of COVID-19, in context", *Prometheus Shrugged* (5/22/2021). <https://prometheusshrugged.substack.com/p/wuhans-house-of-cards-the-outbreak>

This analysis includes *only* data from the Chinese National Health Commission, Chinese Red Cross and peer-reviewed studies published in academic journals. All sources were accessed online and publicly accessible *sans* paywall when added to this analysis, though such open access remains subject to change as measures enacted during the pandemic have begun to be rolled back.

The usage of Chinese-only sources was not intentional; rather, it was a natural result arising from the type of studies from which case data was obtained.

In total, 65 separate sources contained case and death data that were recorded by this author, but there were several hospitals at which multiple studies had been conducted; only the largest number of cases and/or deaths at each location was included in the primary analysis.

Results

The by-district aggregated data is shown below, followed by the data supporting each of the conclusions:

38 aggregated official/peer-reviewed studies								
District	All Cases - (HCW) & (FangCang)		Health Care Worker (HCW)		FangCang Cases		Total	
	Other Cx	%	Cases	%	FangCang	%	Cases	%
Jiangnan	2,116	6.28%	382	12.52%	1,828	11.47%	4,326	8.21%
Jiang'an	3,603	10.69%	685	22.45%	409	2.57%	4,697	8.91%
Qiaokou	5,014	14.88%	554	18.16%	0	0.00%	5,568	10.57%
Hanyang	1,306	3.88%	161	5.28%	2,148	13.48%	3,615	6.86%
Dongxihu	3,363	9.98%	67	2.20%	1,738	10.91%	5,168	9.81%
Caidian	446	1.32%	25	0.82%	3,059	19.20%	3,530	6.70%
Huangpi	442	1.31%	62	2.03%	0	0.00%	504	0.96%
Xinzhou	397	1.18%	8	0.26%	0	0.00%	405	0.77%
Hannan	153	0.45%	6	0.20%	0	0.00%	159	0.30%
Wuchang	8,403	24.93%	542	17.76%	2,124	13.33%	11,069	21.01%
Hongshan	6,358	18.87%	182	5.97%	2,521	15.82%	9,061	17.20%
Qingshan	730	2.17%	263	8.62%	0	0.00%	993	1.88%
Jiangxia	1,371	4.07%	114	3.74%	2,108	13.23%	3,593	6.82%
West [Mkt]	16,840	49.97%	1,950	63.91%	9,182	57.62%	27,972	53.09%
East [WIV]	16,862	50.03%	1,101	36.09%	6,753	42.38%	24,716	46.91%
	33,702		3,051		15,935		52,688	

3 By-District breakdown of the 3 input categories

4 Fig. 1 repeated, for reference

In the official¹⁵ final numbers, the W-E proportions were 63.49% to 36.51%; in the aggregated analysis, the proportions are 53.09% to 46.91%. It is important to note that the former data is from a single source, while the latter numbers come from 38 separate sources; in addition, the authors of most of those 38 sources were doctors who were reporting data from patients treated at their own hospitals, directly from treatment records. There would seem to be no incentive for those authors to collaborate to manipulate statistics that, if ever aggregated, would contradict official case totals reported by the Wuhan CDC to the National Health Commission.

As an aside, the 5 districts that are highlighted in the figure above are not the only ones in which case numbers shifted when comparing the official data to the aggregate totals; however, in both cases [East and West], the other districts' changes have the net effect of canceling themselves out. This may be a function of how Fangcang cases were reported; however, this cannot explain the W-E discrepancy.

¹⁵ Fang Li et al, "Household transmission of SARS-CoV-2 and risk factors for susceptibility and infectivity in Wuhan: a retrospective observational study", *Lancet Infectious Diseases* (1/18/2021). <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33476567/> [from the supplementary files; this represents the latest published set of data pulled from the NHC database]

The aggregated epidemiological data depicts a geospatial distribution that is incongruent with official Chinese data.

AGGREGATED CASE & DEATH DATA FOR THE WUHAN COVID-19 OUTBREAK

Data from 167 Hospitals, across 97 Sub-Districts, from Chinese Censor-Approved Sources

District	ADM	Lat	Long	Hospital	Hospital [Translated]	Tier	Cat	District	Cx	Ptns	Dx	HCW Conf.
Wuchang	42010602	30.541	114.306	Wuhan University People's Hospital	Renmin Hospital [Wu U]	3	A Gen	Wuchang	205	5,510	147	
Qiaokou	42010405	30.586	114.267	Wuhan Tongji Hospital	Tongji	3	A Gen	Qiaokou	156	2,977	70	
Dongxihu	42011214	30.672	114.292	Wuhan Golden & Silver Lake Hospital	Jinyintan	3	A Inf D	Dongxihu	21	2,469	238	
Hongshan	42011103	30.623	114.377	Hubei Maternal/Child Health Hospital	Hubei Maternal/Child [Opt. Valley]	3	A Comm	Hongshan	16	1,765	32	
Jiang'an	42010202	30.587	114.301	Wuhan Central Hospital	Wuhan Central	3	A Gen	Jiang'an	293	1,550	40	
Qiaokou	42010406	30.601	114.200	Wuhan 1st Hospital	Wuhan 1st Hospital	3	A Gen	Qiaokou	102	1,476		
Hongshan	42011102	30.505	114.418	Wuhan 3rd Hospital (光谷院区)	Wuhan 3rd [Gaunggu]	3	A Gen	Hongshan	4	1,241	70	
Wuchang	42010612	30.559	114.359	Wuhan Zhongnan Hospital	Zhongnan [Wu U]	3	A Gen	Wuchang	98	1,181	30	
Jianghan	42010307	30.620	114.280	Wuhan Red Cross Hospital	Wuhan Red Cross	2	A Gen	Jianghan	105	954	78	
Jiang'an	42010207	30.606	114.297	Wuhan 6th Hospital	Wuhan 6th	3	B Gen	Jiang'an	49	891	63	
Jiangxia	42011518	30.448	114.448	Wuhan U. People's Hospital - East [old]	Tongji Hospital [Optics Valley Branch]	3	A Gen	Jiangxia	3	825		
Hongshan	42011102	30.511	114.415	4th PLA General Hospital	4th PLA General H [source pending release]	3	A Gen	Hongshan		816		
Hongshan	42011102	30.511	114.415	Hubei Central Hospital	Hubei People's/Provincial	3	A TCM	Hongshan	40	794		
Jianghan	42010308	30.590	114.281	Wuhan Concord Hospital	Wuhan Concord	3	A Gen	Jianghan	91	791		
Hongshan	42011116	30.507	114.371	Hubei Cancer Hospital	Hubei Cancer Hospital	3	A Onco	Hongshan	6	761		
Jiang'an	42010212	30.634	114.327	Wuhan Hankou Hospital	Hankou Hospital	2	A Gen	Jiang'an	54	602	63	
Dongxihu	42011201	30.622	114.140	Changqing St Health Hospital, East-West Lake	Wuhan 4th [Changqing Branch]	1	A Comm	Dongxihu	1	569		
Hanyang	42010507	30.554	114.278	Wuhan 5th Hospital	Wuhan 5th	3	A Gen	Hanyang	79	500		
Wuchang	42010610	30.609	114.348	Wuhan Wuchang Hospital	Wuchang Hospital	3	A Gen	Wuchang	34	481		
Qiaokou	42010409	30.575	114.261	Hubei 3rd People's Hospital	Hubei 3rd People's	3	A Gen	Qiaokou	116	459	13	
Huangpi	42011601	30.878	114.383	WuhanHuangxuan中医医院	Huangppi TCM	3	A TCM	Huangpi	10	442		
Hanyang	42010511	30.507	114.210	Wuhan Yaxin General Hospital	Wuhan Yaxin Hospital	3	A Gen	Hanyang	28	440		
Qingshan	42010710	30.625	114.367	Wuhan 9th Hospital	Wuhan 9th Hospital	2	A Gen	Qingshan	17	408		
Jiang'an	42010209	30.635	114.312	Hubei TCM/Western Hospital	Hubei TCM	3	A Gen	Jianghan	40	371		
Hanyang	42010502	30.555	114.252	Wuhan Hanyang Hospital	Hanyang Hospital - W/TCM	3	B Gen	Hanyang	43	366		
Wuchang	42010602	30.531	114.333	Tianyousi Hospital	Wuhan Tianyou	3	A Gen	Wuchang	11	362	29	
Hongshan	42011103	30.523	114.356	WuhanHongshan中医医院	Hongshan TCM	3	A TCM	Hongshan	6	344		
Wuchang	42010603	30.546	114.310	Wuhan 3rd Hospital	Wuhan 3rd [Shouwi]	3	A Gen	Wuchang	89	334	26	
Caidian	42011401	30.559	114.139	Wuhan Xintian Hospital	Caidian Maternity Hospital [Xintian]	2	B Comm	Caidian	3	333		
Hongshan	42011104	30.527	114.374	Hubei 672 TCM/Ortho Hospital	Hubei 672	3	A Ortho	Hongshan	7	305		
Wuchang	42010612	30.548	114.338	Wuhan 7th Hospital	Wuhan 7th	2	A Gen	Wuchang	69	297	51	
Jiangxia	42011501	30.377	114.327	Wuhan Jiangxia 1st People's Hospital	Jiangxia 1st People's	3	A Gen	Jiangxia	44	296	22	
Hongshan	42011110	30.591	114.428	Wuhan肺科医院	Wuhan Lung [Pulm.]	3	B Inf D	Hongshan	12	273	45	
Xinzhou	42011701	30.858	114.812	WuhanNew Island中医医院	Xinzhou TCM	2	A TCM	Xinzhou	2	267		
Jiangxia	42011504	30.349	114.324	Wuhan Jiangxia TCM	Jiangxia TCM	2	A TCM	Jiangxia	52	250		
Dongxihu	42011217	30.644	114.161	Wuhan Taikang Hospital	Wuhan Taikang	2	A Gen	Dongxihu	7	246		
Wuchang	42010609	30.587	114.335	Wuhan Bauhinia Hospital	Wuhan Bauhinia	3	A Gen	Wuchang	9	238		
Jiang'an	42010208	30.609	114.313	Wuhan 8th Hospital	Wuhan 8th	2	A Gen	Jiang'an	47	216		
Jiang'an	42010207	30.608	114.294	Wuhan Children's Hospital	Wuhan Childrens' Hospital	3	A Gen	Jiang'an	30	191		
Jiang'an	42010213	30.612	114.294	Yangtze River Shipping General Hospital	Yangtze River Shipping General Hospital	3	B Gen	Jiang'an	82	153		
Hannan	42011308	30.319	114.080	Hannan People's Hospital	Hannan Peoples' Hospital	2	B Gen	Hannan	6	153		
Qingshan	42010709	30.620	114.482	WISCO 2nd Staff Hospital	WISCO 2nd Staff Hospital	3	B Gen	Qingshan	79	146	7	
Xinzhou	42011701	30.849	114.810	WuhanNew Island人民医院	Xinzhou Peoples' Hospital	2	A Gen	Xinzhou	3	130	11	
Qiaokou	42010415	30.572	114.273	Wuhan 4th Hospital	Wuhan 4th Hospital	3	A Gen	Qiaokou	115	102	3	
Qingshan	42010702	30.638	114.410	China Resources Wugang General Hospital	Wugang General Hospital	3	A Gen	Qingshan	99	100		
Dongxihu	42011212	30.655	114.139	Dongxihu People's Hospital	Wuhan Union Peoples' Hospital - West	3	B Gen	Dongxihu	19	79		
Qingshan	42010701	30.638	114.387	Puren Hospital, 武汉市普仁医院	Wuhan Puren Hospital	3	A Gen	Qingshan	58	76		
Hongshan	42011107	30.589	114.385	Wuhan Pear Garden Hospital	Wuhan Pear Garden	3	A Gen	Hongshan	39	59		
Caidian	42011411	30.568	114.051	Wuhan Caidian People's Hospital	Caidian Branch [Tongji]	2	A Gen	Caidian	15	59	41	
Caidian	42011401	30.578	114.039	Wuhan Caidian Grand Street Health Hospital	Wuhan Jihe [W/TCM]	2	A Comm	Caidian	1	54		
Jianghan	42010306	30.589	114.289	Wuhan Asian Heart Hospital	Wuhan Asian Heart Hospital	3	A Heart	Jianghan	75			
Jianghan	42010311	30.634	114.272	Wuhan Central Hospital - Backyard Area	Center Hospital Back Lake Hospital	3	A Gen	Jianghan	35			
Huangpi	42011601	30.894	114.377	Huangpi People's Hospital	Huangxuan People's Hospital	3	B Gen	Huangpi	32			
Jiang'an	42010209	30.631	114.315	Wuhan Mental Health Center	Wuhan Mental Health Center	3	A Psych	Jiang'an	30			
Jiang'an	42010203	30.594	114.304	Wuhan TCM Hospital	Wuhan TCM Hospital	3	A TCM	Jiang'an	27			
Jianghan	42010307	30.574	114.298	Wuhan Commercial Hospital	Wuhan Commercial Hospital	2	A Comm	Jianghan	23			
Jianghan	42010311	30.621	114.267	武汉济民老年医院	Wuhan Jimin Hospital for the Elderly	2	A Comm	Jianghan	18			
Hongshan	42011116	30.512	114.384	Hubei Rongjun Hospital	Rongjun Hospital, Hubei Prv	2	A Gen	Hongshan	17			
Jianghan	42010311	30.623	114.267	Wuhan You Care Hospital	Wuhan Yufu Hospital	2	A Gen	Jianghan	17			
Qiaokou	42010403	30.591	114.223	Wuhan Qiaokou Hanjiayu Street CHSC	Han Jiaxuan St CHSC, Lukou	1	A Comm	Qiaokou	15			
Qiaokou	42010416	30.588	114.221	Qiaokou Gutian Street CHSC	Gutian St CHSC, Lukou	1	A Comm	Qiaokou	11			
Dongxihu	42011214	30.656	114.261	WuhanDongxihu第二人民医院	2nd People's Hospital of East-West Lake	2	A Gen	Dongxihu	10			
Jiang'an	42010213	30.606	114.287	WuhanJiang'an台北街社区卫生服务中心	Taipei St CHSC, Riverside	1	A Comm	Jiang'an	10			
Qiaokou	42010403	30.581	114.250	Wuhan Renai Hospital	Wuhan Renai Hospital	2	A Gen	Qiaokou	10			
Hongshan	42011102	30.512	114.418	Wuhan Changying Hospital	Wuhan Changying Hospital	2	A Gen	Hongshan	9			
Wuchang	42010612	30.550	114.352	Hubei direct authority	Hubei Prv directly under the organ hospital	2	A Gen	Wuchang	9			
Hanyang	42010509	30.581	114.198	WuhanHanyang琴断口街社区卫生服务中心	Qinkou St CHSC, Hanyang	1	A Comm	Hanyang	7			
Qiaokou	42010405	30.583	114.269	WuhanQiaokou宝丰街社区卫生服务中心	Baofeng St CHSC, Lukou	1	A Comm	Qiaokou	7			
Jiangxia	42011501	30.355	114.315	WuhanJiangxia纸坊卫生院	Paper House Health Hospital, Jiangxia	1	A Comm	Jiangxia	6			
Qiaokou	42010405	30.590	114.259	Hubei Wuhan F Sub-prison Hospital	Wuhan Women's Prison Hospital, Hubei Prv	2	B Comm	Qiaokou	6			
Hongshan	42011102	30.490	114.328	Huazhong Ag. U. CHSC	CHSC of Huazhong Ag U, Lion Mountain St	1	A Comm	Hongshan	5			
Qingshan	42010704	30.643	114.408	Wuhan Qingshan Red Steel City Street CHSC	Red Steel City St CHSC in Qingshan	1	A Comm	Qingshan	5			
Hongshan	42011116	30.511	114.397	WuhanHongshan卓刀泉街卫生中心	Zhuo Daoquan St CHC in Hongshan	1	A Comm	Hongshan	4			
Jiang'an	42010214	30.683	114.379	Jiang'an Family Street CHSC	The CHSC of Yanjiayi St in Jiangjiang	1	A Comm	Jiang'an	4			
Qiaokou	42010403	30.589	114.230	WuhanQiaokou宗关街社区卫生服务中心	Zongguan St CHSC, Lukou	1	A Comm	Qiaokou	4			
Qiaokou	42010406	30.576	114.261	WuhanQiaokou荣华街社区卫生服务中心	Ronghua St CHSC, Lukou	1	A Comm	Qiaokou	4			
Qiaokou	42010409	30.574	114.274	WuhanQiaokou汉中街社区卫生服务中心	Hanzhong St CHSC, Lukou	1	A Comm	Qiaokou	4			
Dongxihu	42011203	30.653	114.039	武汉Dongxihu走马岭街中心卫生院	Wuhan E-W L to walk Maling St CHH	1	A Comm	Dongxihu	3			
Hongshan	42011105	30.496	114.290	WuhanHongshan张家湾街社区卫生服务中心	Zhangjiawan St CHSC in Hongshan	1	A Comm	Hongshan	3			
Huangpi	42011601	30.866	114.393	WuhanHuangxuan木兰乡卫生院	Qianchuan St HH, Huangxuan	1	A Comm	Huangpi	3			
Huangpi	42011606	31.106	114.466	WuhanHuangxuan箭川街道卫生院	Magnolia Township HH in Huangxian	1	A Comm	Huangpi	3			
Jiang'an	42010207	30.607	114.301	WuhanJiang'an劳动街社区卫生服务中心	Labor St CHSC, Riverside	1	A Comm	Jiang'an	3			

Jiang'an	42010211	30.597	114.299	WuhanJiang'an球场街北社区卫生服务中心	CHSC, NorthStadium St, Jiangjiang	1A	Comm	Jiang'an	3
Jianghan	42010305	30.582	114.282	Jianghan Street CHSC	Public Opinion St CHSC, Jianghan	1A	Comm	Jianghan	3
Wuchang	42010603	30.549	114.322	WuhanWuchang疾病预防控制中心	Wuchang CDC, Wuhan	1A	Comm	Wuchang	3
Wuchang	42010603	30.543	114.316	WuhanWuchang首义路街社区卫生服务中心	WuchangWuhan, First Yilu St CHSC	1A	Comm	Wuchang	3
Wuchang	42010611	30.556	114.316	Hubei Central Hospital花园山院区	Garden Mtn Hospital Area, Hubei Central	3A	TCM	Wuchang	3
Caidian	42011402	30.477	113.829	WuhanCaidian侯德街卫生院	Dwarf St Health Hospital in Caidian	1A	Comm	Caidian	2
Caidian	42011407	30.478	113.932	WuhanCaidian永安街村社区卫生室	Park Tree Village HR on Yong'an St, Caidian	1A	Comm	Caidian	2
Dongxihu	42011212	30.679	114.178	Dongxihu River Street Health Hospital	Jinyin Lake St HH in E-W Lake	1A	Comm	Dongxihu	2
Hanyang	42010508	30.576	114.216	WuhanHanyang二桥街社区卫生服务中心	2nd Bridge St CHSC, Hanyang	1A	Comm	Hanyang	2
Huangpi	42011601	30.624	114.306	武汉黄浦中西医结合妇产医院	Wuhan Huangpu W/TCM & Maternity H	2A	Gen	Huangpi	2
Huangpi	42011605	30.983	114.449	WuhanHuangxuan王家河街道卫生院	Wangjiahe St Health Hospital, Huangxian	1A	Comm	Huangpi	2
Huangpi	42011613	30.888	114.382	WuhanHuangxuan天河卫生院	Tianhe HH, Huangxian	1A	Comm	Huangpi	2
Huangpi	42011618	30.737	114.264	Huangpi People's Hospital (盘龙分院)	Huangxuan People's H (Panlong Branch)	3B	Gen	Huangpi	2
Jiang'an	42010208	30.613	114.317	WuhanJiang'an永清街社区卫生服务中心	Yongqing St CHSC, Jiangjiang	1A	Comm	Jiang'an	2
Jiang'an	42010210	30.598	114.312	Hubei Armed Police HQ Hospital	Hubei Provincial Armed Police Hq Hospital	3A	Gen	Jiang'an	2
Jiang'an	42010217	30.625	114.293	长江水利委员会长江医院	Yangtze River Water Resources Commission	2B	Comm	Jiang'an	2
Jiang'an	42010218	30.619	114.297	武汉弘济骨科医院	Wuhan Hongji Orthopaedic Hospital	3A	Ortho	Jiang'an	2
Jianghan	42010301	30.577	114.289	WuhanJianghan满春街社区卫生服务中心	Manchun St CHSC, Jianghan	1A	Comm	Jianghan	2
Jianghan	42010302	30.582	114.296	CHSC of Civil Rights St, Jianghan	CHSC of Civil Rights St, Jianghan	1A	Comm	Jianghan	2
Jianghan	42010313	30.613	114.248	WuhanJianghan常青街社区卫生服务中心	Evergreen St CHSC, Jianghan	1A	Comm	Jianghan	2
Jiangxia	42011501	30.353	114.323	WuhanJiangxia妇幼保健院	Women's & Children's HH in Jiangxia	1A	Comm	Jiangxia	2
Jiangxia	42011504	30.252	114.342	WuhanJiangxia马龙潭卫生院	Health Hospital, Jiangxia	1A	Comm	Jiangxia	2
Jiangxia	42011517	30.406	114.421	WuhanJiangxia麓龙岛社区卫生服务中心	Tibetan Long Island CHSC in Jiangxia	1A	Comm	Jiangxia	2
Qingshan	42010701	30.641	114.334	Wuhan Puren Riverside Hospital	Puren RiverBank Hospital	2A	Gen	Qingshan	2
Wuchang	42010607	30.561	114.312	WuhanWuchang积玉桥街社区卫生服务中心	Yuqiao St CHSC, Wuchang	1A	Comm	Wuchang	2
Wuchang	42010613	30.535	114.379	Hubei Geological Staff Hospital	Hubei Geological Staff Hospital	2B	Comm	Wuchang	2
Caidian	42011406	30.516	114.103	Daji St Health Hospital in Caidian	Daji St Health Hospital in Caidian	1A	Comm	Caidian	1
Caidian	42011409	30.414	114.095	Military Hill Street Health Hospital, Wuhan EDZ	Military Hill St Health Hospital, Wuhan EDZ	1A	Comm	Caidian	1
Dongxihu	42011208	30.656	114.261	Xin'an Du St Health Hospital, East-West Lake	Xin'an du St Health Hospital, E-W Lake	1A	Comm	Dongxihu	1
Dongxihu	42011210	30.733	114.130	WuhanDongxihu柏泉街卫生院	ParkQuan St Health Hospital, E-W Lake	1A	Comm	Dongxihu	1
Dongxihu	42011211	30.626	114.143	WuhanDongxihu金湖街卫生院	Weihe St Health Hospital in E-W Lake	1A	Comm	Dongxihu	1
Dongxihu	42011215	30.684	114.169	WuhanDongxihu长青街卫生院	Wuhan East-West Lake Trail River St Health	1A	Comm	Dongxihu	1
Hanyang	42010507	30.503	114.325	WuhanHanyang万松街社区卫生服务中心	Wansong St CHSC, Hanyang	1A	Comm	Hanyang	1
Hanyang	42010507	30.558	114.282	Jianqiao St CHSC, Hanyang	Jianqiao St CHSC, Hanyang	1A	Comm	Hanyang	1
Hongshan	42011102	30.513	114.416	WuhanHongshan关山街长动社区卫生服务中心	Changying CHSC on Guanshan St, Hongshan	1A	Comm	Hongshan	1
Hongshan	42011103	30.535	114.371	WuhanHongshan王兵西医内科诊所	Wang Bingxi Medical Clinic in Hongshan	1A	Comm	Hongshan	1
Hongshan	42011104	30.480	114.360	华中农业大学社区卫生服务中心	CHSC, Central Agricultural U of China	1A	Comm	Hongshan	1
Hongshan	42011104	30.514	114.355	中建三局武汉中心医院	China Construction Bureau Wuhan Central	2B	Gen	Hongshan	1
Hongshan	42011105	30.493	114.299	WuhanHongshan张家湾街光耀社区卫生服务中心	Zhangjiawan St Guangxia CHSS in Hongshan	1A	Comm	Hongshan	1
Hongshan	42011107	30.623	114.398	Wuhan梨园社区卫生服务中心	Pear Garden CHSC,	1A	Comm	Hongshan	1
Hongshan	42011108	30.515	114.331	武汉方泰医院	Wuhan Fangtai Hospital	2A	Gen	Hongshan	1
Hongshan	42011112	30.515	114.377	Wuhan东湖新技术开发区佛祖岭社区服务中心	Wuhan East Lake H-T DZ Buddha Zuling CSC	1A	Comm	Hongshan	1
Hongshan	42011112	30.500	114.430	Wuhan东湖新技术开发区左岭街社区卫生服务中心	Zuoling St HSC, East Lake H-T DZ	1A	Comm	Hongshan	1
Hongshan	42011114	30.543	114.527	Wuhan东湖新技术开发区花山街社区卫生服务中心	Huashan St CHSC, East Lake H-T DZ	1A	Comm	Hongshan	1
Hongshan	42011114	30.543	114.527	Wuhan东湖新技术开发区花山街社区卫生服务中心	Huashan St CHSC, East Lake H-T DZ	1A	Comm	Hongshan	1
Hongshan	42011117	30.590	114.381	武汉厚德康医院	Wuhan HouDekang Hospital	2B	Comm	Hongshan	1
Hongshan	42011117	30.558	114.420	Wuhan东湖生态旅游风景区第二社区卫生服务站	2nd CHSC of East Lake Eco-SA	1A	Comm	Hongshan	1
Hongshan	42011119	30.470	114.386	武汉东湖新技术开发区关东街龙城社区卫生服务站	Wuhan E-L H-T DZ Kanto St Longcheng CHSC	1A	Comm	Hongshan	1
Huangpi	42011601	30.892	114.378	WuhanHuangxuan妇幼保健院	Women's & Children's HH in Huangxian	1A	Comm	Huangpi	1
Huangpi	42011601	30.896	114.375	WuhanHuangxuan荆川街环城社区卫生服务站	CHSC of Qianchuan St Ring City in Huangxua	1A	Comm	Huangpi	1
Huangpi	42011603	31.260	114.386	WuhanHuangxuan姚家集街道卫生院	Yaojiaji St HH in Huangxian	1A	Comm	Huangpi	1
Huangpi	42011612	30.810	114.301	WuhanHuangxuan槐店街社区卫生服务站	Hengdian St CHH, Huangxian	1A	Comm	Huangpi	1
Huangpi	42011616	30.772	114.439	武汉黄陂三里桥街社区卫生室	Wuhan Huangxuan Sanliqiao St HH	1A	Comm	Huangpi	1
Huangpi	42011616	30.748	114.426	WuhanHuangxuan三里桥街邓堰村卫生室	HR, Deng Wei Village, Sanliqiao St, Huangxu	1A	Comm	Huangpi	1
Jiang'an	42010206	30.599	114.294	WuhanJiang'an西马街社区卫生服务中心	Xima St CHSC, Riverside	1A	Comm	Jiang'an	1
Jiang'an	42010207	30.608	114.306	WuhanJiang'an劳动街赵家巷社区卫生服务站	Zhaojia-bin CHSC, Labor St, Jiangjiang	1A	Comm	Jiang'an	1
Jiang'an	42010212	30.654	114.337	武汉岱山医院	Wuhan Lushan Hospital	1A	Comm	Jiang'an	1
Jiang'an	42010212	30.654	114.338	武汉Jiang'an丹水池街社区卫生服务中心	Danshui Pool St CHSC, Wuhan Riverside	1A	Comm	Jiang'an	1
Jiang'an	42010219	30.644	114.294	WuhanJiang'an塔子湖街社区卫生服务中心	Tazihu St CHSC, Riverside	1A	Comm	Jiang'an	1
Jianghan	42010306	30.601	114.271	Wuhan第一口腔医院	Wuhan 1st Oral Hospital	3B	Oral	Jianghan	1
Jianghan	42010306	30.584	114.289	WuhanJianghan前进街社区卫生服务中心	Forward St CHSC, Jianghan	1A	Comm	Jianghan	1
Jianghan	42010307	30.579	114.296	WuhanJianghan民族街社区卫生服务中心	CHSC of National St, Jianghan	1A	Comm	Jianghan	1
Jianghan	42010308	30.591	114.286	Wuhan Emergency Center	Wuhan Emergency Center	1A	Comm	Jianghan	1
Jianghan	42010308	30.594	114.287	WuhanJianghan新华街社区卫生服务中心	Xinhua St CHSC, Jianghan	1A	Comm	Jianghan	1
Jianghan	42010309	30.587	114.275	Jianghan Wansong Street CHSC	Wansong St CHSC, Jianghan	1A	Comm	Jianghan	1
Jianghan	42010309	30.593	114.273	WuhanJianghan万松街社区卫生中心	Wansong St CHC, Jianghan	1A	Comm	Jianghan	1
Jianghan	42010310	30.595	114.286	WuhanJianghan疾病预防控制中心	CDC, Jianghan	1A	Comm	Jianghan	1
Jianghan	42010313	30.636	114.268	WuhanJianghan汉兴街社区卫生服务中心第二	Chang II CHSS, Hanxing St CHSC, Jianghan	1A	Comm	Jianghan	1
Jiangxia	42011501	30.382	114.329	WuhanJiangxia疾病预防控制中心	CDC, Jiangxia	1A	Comm	Jiangxia	1
Jiangxia	42011504	30.264	114.350	Jiangxia Ulongquan Health Hospital LH Branch	Wulongquan HH Land Branch, Jiangxia	B	Comm	Jiangxia	1
Jiangxia	42011513	30.411	114.315	Wuhan Jiangxia EDZ New Area CHSC	CHSC of Bridge New Area, Jiangxia EDZ	1A	Comm	Jiangxia	1
Qiaokou	42010403	30.583	114.247	三六〇西医院	3604 Hospital	3A	Gen	Qiaokou	1
Qiaokou	42010404	30.580	114.249	WuhanQiaokou汉水桥街社区卫生服务中心	Hanshuiqiao St CHSC, Lukou	1A	Comm	Qiaokou	1
Qiaokou	42010414	30.577	114.271	WuhanQiaokou长风街社区卫生服务中心	Changfeng St CSC, Lukou	1A	Comm	Qiaokou	1
Qiaokou	42010415	30.572	114.273	武汉普爱医院	Wuhan Puai Hospital	3A	Gen	Qiaokou	1
Qingshan	42010703	30.639	114.404	WuhanQingshan新沟桥街社区卫生服务中心	Xingouqiao St CHSC, Qingshan	1A	Comm	Qingshan	1
Qingshan	42010707	30.619	114.443	WuhanQingshan厂前街社区卫生服务中心	Wuhan Qingshan Factory Front St CHSC	1A	Comm	Qingshan	1
Qingshan	42010708	30.581	114.469	Wuhan武东医院	Wudong Hospital	2A	Psych	Qingshan	1
Wuchang	42010601	30.530	114.302	WuhanWuchang白沙洲街社区卫生服务中心	Baishazhou St CHSC, Wuchang	1A	Comm	Wuchang	1
Wuchang	42010610	30.607	114.351	WuhanWuchang杨园街第二社区卫生服务中心	2nd CHSC on Yangyuan St, Wuchang	1A	Comm	Wuchang	1
Wuchang	42010610	30.613	114.363	Wuchang Yangyuan Street Wuhan U. S&T CHSC	Wuhan U of Technology CHSC, Yangyuan St	1A	Comm	Wuchang	1
Wuchang	42010611	30.545	114.340	WuhanWuchang中南路街南湖社区卫生服务站	South Lake CHSC, Zhongnan Road St	1A	Comm	Wuchang	1
Wuchang	42010613	30.535	114.343	武汉武钢医院	Wuhan Wupan Hospital	2B	Gen	Wuchang	1
Xinzhou	42011701	30.846	114.812	WuhanNew Island锦城社区卫生服务中心	Xinzhou Lucheng Health Service Center	1A	Comm	Xinzhou	1
Xinzhou	42011713	30.683	114.590	Hubei Yangluo Central Hospital	Yangluo Central Hospital, Hubei Prv	2A	Gen	Xinzhou	1
Xinzhou	42011713	30.674	114.577	WuhanNew Island阳逻社区卫生服务中心	Yanglu CHSC, Xinzhou	1A	Comm	Xinzhou	1

LEGEND

Dist	District [West or East]
Lat	Latitude
Long	Longitude
ADM	Administrative Division Code
Hospital	Hospital name in the original source
Hospital [Tr]	Hospital [translated]
Tier	Hospital [size] level 3A>1B
Cat	Hospital focus [general, community, etc]
Dist	District [West or East]
HCW Cx	Confirmed Health-Care Worker cases
Conf Cx	Confirmed Cases
Conf DX	Confirmed Deaths

Study details from the included sources:

					Cases			
					Counted	Expected	A Expected	Deaths
					15,935	12,000	122.8%	74
					3,051	3,058	99.8%	23
					33,702	37,022	91.0%	1,079
					52,688	50,340	104.7%	1,176
					1,176	3,869	30.4%	
					-345	-0.64%		

					Official Wuhan CDC Source or Peer-Reviewed Study			
Fangcang Hospital								
F	1	Hubeishan Fangcang	3,059	69	2/8/2020	4/14/2020		The epidemiological problem with COVID-19: ocular infection. Moderate clinical manifestation and potential infection risk
F	2	Lishibanshan Fangcang	2,011		2/8/2020	4/14/2020		The health and economic impact of constructing temporary field hospitals to meet the COVID-19 pandemic surge. Wuhan, Lishibanshan Hospital in China as a case study
F	3	Jiangjia Fangcang	1,848		2/11/2020	3/10/2020	Total patients admitted: 1848	The worldwide coronavirus disease 2019 outbreak: Advice and recommendation on radiology management and infection control from makeshift hospitals in Wuhan
F	4	Jiangnan Fangcang	1,828		2/5/2020	3/9/2020		Clinical characteristics and prognostic factors of COVID-19 patients progression to severe: a retrospective, observational study
F	5	Jiangnan Fangcang	1,738		2/7/2020	2/26/2020		Characteristics of 1738 Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) in Wuhan, China
F	6	East Lake West Lake Fangcang	1,682		2/4/2020	3/10/2020	conf. non-critically ill pts	Nepidemiological Implications of Non-critically Ill Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 in a Fangcang Shelter Hospital in Wuhan, China
F	7	Wuchang Fangcang	1,124		2/17/2020	3/8/2020	Nearly 1,000 patients in total; 100 randomly enrolled	Investigation of 100 SARS-CoV-2 infected families in Wuhan: Transmission patterns and follow-up
F	8	Zhuanzhou Fangcang	1,000	5	2/17/2020	3/8/2020		Deep learning-based triage and analysis of lesion burden for COVID-19: a retrospective study, with external validation
F	9	Guanggu Fangcang	722		2/21/2020	3/6/2020		Clinical characteristics and analysis of risk factors for disease progression of COVID-19: A retrospective Cohort Study
F	10	Jiangnan Fangcang	409		2/11/2020	3/10/2020	Patients in Zone B & C; Only 2 transfer Hosp. until	The worldwide coronavirus disease 2019 outbreak: Advice and recommendation on radiology management and infection control from makeshift hospitals in Wuhan
F	11	Jiaying SS Fangcang	300		2/11/2020	3/10/2020		Follow-up results of 117 patients with novel coronavirus pneumonia after discharge from Wuhan Fangcang Hospital - Chinese Critical Care Emergency Medicine (WuJian.com)
F	12	Houzhai Fangcang	117		1/15/2020	3/10/2020	Consecutively admitted patients with COVID-19	Benefits from Shortening Viral Shedding by Traditional Chinese Medicine Treatment for Moderate COVID-19: An Observational Study
F	13	Jiangnan Fangcang	97		1/15/2020	3/10/2020		
Designated/Other Hospital								
D	1	Reunion Hospital [Wu U]	5,510	147				Sex differences in clinical characteristics and risk factors for mortality among severe patients with COVID-19: a retrospective study
D	2	Tongji	2,977	70	1/3/2020	3/30/2020		Clinical characteristics of 70 fatal patients with COVID-19
D	3	Jiayintan	2,469	238			2,469 pts from 177 - 529, deaths added	1-year outcomes in hospital survivors with COVID-19: a longitudinal cohort study
D	4	Hubei Maternity Child [Opt. Valley]	1,765	32	2/19/2020	3/19/2020	All inpatients during study period	Epidemiologic Characteristics of and Prognostic Factors for COVID-19 Among Hospitalized Patients: Updated Implications From Hubei Province, China
D	5	Wuhan Central	1,550	40	1/1/2020	4/30/2020	Pre-wild-conf. C-19	Analysis of clinical features of COVID-19 in cancer patients
D	6	Wuhan 1st Hospital	1,476		3/19/2020	1/4/2021	COVID-19 patients admitted during the period	Clinical features of 162 fatal cases of COVID-19: a multi-center retrospective study
D	7	Wuhan 3rd [Guanggu]	1,241	70	1/8/2020	3/17/2020	Shouyi & Guanggu combined for 96 deaths	Predicting Progression of COVID-19 Infection to Prioritize Medical Resource Allocation: A Novel Triage Model Based on Patient Characteristics and Symptoms at Presentation
D	8	Zhongshan [Wu U]	1,181	30	12/30/2019	3/10/2020	716 confirmed; 406 clinically diagnosed; 59 missing	Tobacco smoking confers risk for severe COVID-19 pneumonia by pulmonary immune - Li - 2021 - Journal of Internal Medicine - Wiley Online Library
D	9	Wuhan Red Cross	997	78			All Confirmed cases through period	Clinical features and mortality factors of severe novel coronavirus pneumonia
D	10	Wuhan 6th	891	63	December	February	582 severe cases, 159 critical	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	11	Tongji Hospital [Optics Valley Branch]	825				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	[preprint; pending publication]
D	12	4th PLA General Hospital	816				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	13	Hubei People's Provincial	784				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	14	Wuhan Cancer	791				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	15	Hubei Cancer Hospital	761				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	16	Jiangnan Hospital	602	63	11/4/2020	2/29/2020	602 COVID-19 patients with established clinical onset	Elderly Male With Cardiovascular-Related Comorbidities Has a Higher Rate of Fatal Outcomes: A Retrospective Study in 602 Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019
D	17	Wuhan 9th [Changqiao Branch]	500				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	18	Wuhan 5th	500				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	19	Wuchang Hospital	481				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	20	Hubei 3rd People's	459	13	1/19/2020	3/7/2020	459 Consecutive; 132 comorbidities	The characteristics and death risk factors of 132 COVID-19 pneumonia patients with comorbidities: a retrospective single center analysis in Wuhan, China
D	21	Wuhan TCM	442				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	An Advanced Study of Urban Emergency Medical Equipment Logistics Distribution for Different Levels of Urgency Demand
D	22	Wuhan Yantai	440				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	23	Wuhan 9th	408				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	24	Hubei TCM	371				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	25	Jiaying Hospital - WTCM	366				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	26	Wuhan Tianyuan	362	29			Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	27	Tongshan TCM	344				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	28	Wuhan 3rd [Shouyi]	334	26	1/8/2020	3/17/2020	Shouyi & Guanggu combined for 96 deaths	Clinical features of 162 fatal cases of COVID-19: a multi-center retrospective study
D	29	Capital Maternity Hospital [Xintian]	333				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	30	Hubei 6th	305				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	31	Wuhan 7th	297	51			Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	32	Jiangnan 1st People's	206	22	1/7/2020	2/11/2020	277 discharged; consecutive pts	Clinical and Laboratory Predictors of In-hospital Mortality in Patients With Coronavirus Disease-2019: A Cohort Study in Wuhan, China
D	33	Wuhan Liansi [Fujian]	273	45	12/25/2019	2/15/2020		Hospitalization and Critical Care of 109 Decedents with COVID-19 Pneumonia in Wuhan, China
D	34	Xiaohou TCM	267				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	35	Jiangnan TCM	250				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	36	Wuhan Taikang	246				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	37	Wuhan Baoshan	238				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	38	Wuhan 8th	216				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	39	Wuhan Children's Hospital	191				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	40	Hannan Hospital	153	28/2020	3/20/2020	289 COVID-19 Patients from Union West, Hannan		Regional Differences in Epidemiological and Clinical Characteristics, Treatment, and Clinical Outcomes of COVID-19 in Wuhan and Remote Areas of Hubei Province
D	41	Yantai River Shuangji	153				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	42	WISCO 2nd Staff Hospital	146	7				Clinical characteristics and co-factors of 24 hospitalized patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a retrospective cohort study - ScienceDirect
D	43	Xiaohou People's Hospital	127	11	1/16/2020	2/25/2020		COVID-19 is Distinct From SARS-CoV-2-Negative Community-Acquired Pneumonia
D	44	Wuhan 4th	102	3	1/10/2020	3/15/2020		Analysis of clinical characteristics and laboratory findings of 95 cases of 2019 novel coronavirus pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a retrospective analysis
D	45	Wuyang General Hospital	100				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	A comparative analysis of clinical characteristics in patients infected with severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) between Wuhan and Zhouzhan, China
D	46	Wuhan Union West	99		2/8/2020	3/20/2020		Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
D	47	Wuhan Pating	76		Late January Early February	A total of 76 confirmed patients		Regional Differences in Epidemiological and Clinical Characteristics, Treatment, and Clinical Outcomes of COVID-19 in Wuhan and Remote Areas of Hubei Province
D	48	Chuanxin Branch [Tongji]	59	4	2/2/2020	3/2/2020	ICU admissions during the period	Clinical Features and CT Imaging Analysis of 76 Patients with Corona Virus Disease 19 (COVID-19) in a Designated RMPH (Jiaying.com)
D	49	Wuhan Peier Garden	59				Census (Occ. Beds; high # of Feb. 14th-16th)	Critically Ill Patients with Coronavirus Disease 2019 in a Designated RMPH (Jiaying.com)
D	50	Wuhan Jie [WTCM]	54	1/24/2020	2/17/2020	Only 2 transfer Hosp. until 2/1/20		Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226
Additional studies at listed hospitals (only largest values kept for the primary list)					Official Wuhan CDC Source or Peer-Reviewed Study			
		Hospital	Cx	Dx	From	To	Criteria/Notes	
		Tongji	2000	70	1/15/2020	2/25/2020	More than 2000 patients treated since mid-January	Clinical characteristics of 70 fatal patients with COVID-19
		Tongji	1,647		2/1/2020	3/3/2020		Deep learning-based triage and analysis of lesion burden for COVID-19: a retrospective study, with external validation
		Reunion Hospital [Wu U]	1,530	147	1/1/2020	4/10/2020		Sex differences in clinical characteristics and risk factors for mortality among severe patients with COVID-19: a retrospective study
		Tongji	1,479		1/10/2020	3/8/2020	cases admitted to Tongji	Development and Validation of a Prognostic Risk Score System for COVID-19 Inpatients: A Multi-Center Retrospective Study in China
		Jiayintan	1,476	238	12/30/2019	2/25/2020	Consecutive patients who discharged or died by 2/27	Incidence, risk factors and prognosis of acute kidney injury in severe and critically ill patients with COVID-19
		Jiangnan Fangcang	1,320		2/5/2020	3/9/2020	1,828 total diagnosed	Clinical characteristics and outcomes of COVID-19 patients with gastrointestinal symptoms admitted to Jiangnan Fangcang Shelter Hospital in Wuhan, China
		Jiayintan	1,150	157	12/29/2019	2/28/2020	Laboratory-confirmed patients with determined onset	Clinical outcomes of COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a large cohort study
		Dongshui Fangcang	1,102		2/7/2020	2/12/2020	non-critically ill	
		Dongshui Fangcang	714		2/7/2020	3/6/2020	mild to moderate	
		Jiayintan	471		1/1/2020	2/5/2020	Discharged prior to 2/6/20 [160 severe/critical, 159	Diagnosis and treatment of 471 patients with 2019 novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19)
		Wuhan 5th	427					An Advanced Study of Urban Emergency Medical Equipment Logistics Distribution for Different Levels of Urgency Demand
		Reunion Hospital [Wu U]	354	11	2/4/2020	2/28/2020		Clinical characteristics and co-factors of 24 hospitalized patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a retrospective cohort study - ScienceDirect
		Wuhan Red Cross	304		2/1/2020	3/15/2020	Cases diagnosed during the period	COVID-19 is Distinct From SARS-CoV-2-Negative Community-Acquired Pneumonia
		Tianyuan	301	29	12/25/2019	2/15/2020		Hospitalization and Critical Care of 109 Decedents with COVID-19 Pneumonia in Wuhan, China - PMC (nih.gov)
		Jiayintan	295		1/24/2020	3/1/2020	188 moderate; 90 severe & 17 critical	Factors Defining the Development of Severe Illness in Patients with COVID-19: A Retrospective Study
		Zhongshan [Wu U] & Central	245		12/26/2019	2/15/2020		Association of D-dimer elevation with inflammation and organ dysfunction in ICU patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a multicenter study
		Jiayintan	210	93	1/23/2020	4/6/2020	All pts with-conf COVID-19 adm. To ICU during	The incidence, risk factors and prognosis of acute kidney injury in severe and critically ill patients with COVID-19 in mainland China: a retrospective study
		Jiayintan	201	44	12/25/2019	1/26/2020	201 pts w/conf C-19 pneumonia, adm. To Jiu. during	Risk Factors Associated With Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome and Death in Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 Pneumonia in Wuhan, China
		Jiayintan	180	89	12/30/2019	3/11/2020	patients with proven COVID-19 in the ICU	COVID-19-associated coagulopathy, thrombocytopenia, prothrombin and poor prognosis in ICU
		Jiayintan	158	77	1/20/2020	2/26/2020	patients with proven COVID-19 in the ICU	Association of D-dimer elevation with inflammation and organ dysfunction in ICU patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a retrospective observational study
		Jiayintan	141		1/20/2020	3/6/2020	fatal cases	Clinical characteristics of 141 deaths from novel coronavirus pneumonia in Wuhan Jiyintan Hospital
		Zhongshan [Wu U]	138	6	1/1/2020	1/28/2020	138 hospitalized patients [consecutive]	Clinical Characteristics of 138 Hospitalized Patients With 2019 Novel Coronavirus-Infected Pneumonia in Wuhan, China
		Jiayintan	135	46	12/29/2019	1/31/2020	discharged or died by 1/31/2020; 813 adult patients	Were hospitalized in Jiu. or W. L. mg before 1/31/2020
		Jiayintan	134		12/30/2019	2/20/2020	critically ill in ICU	Retrospective analysis of clinical features in 134 coronavirus disease 2019 cases
		Union	118					
		Jiayintan	99		1/7/2020	1/20/2020	First 99 patients' data compared	A cross-sectional comparison of epidemiological and clinical features of patients with coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in Wuhan and outside Wuhan, China
		Jiayintan	99	11	1/7/2020	1/20/2020	All conf. cases through 1/20/20	Epidemiological and clinical characteristics of 99 cases of 2019 novel coronavirus pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a descriptive study
		Reunion Hospital [Wu U]	92		1/6/2020	1/25/2020		Analysis of 92 deceased patients with COVID-19
		WISCO 2nd [Qichangou]	83	7	1/28/2020	2/26/2020	Only 2 new patients after 1/23/20	Case analysis of novel coronavirus pneumonia in the Second Hospital of Wuhan Iron and Steel Company, Qichangou District, Wuhan, China
		Wuhan 7th	82					Clinical Characteristics of Nutritional Indicators in Patients with Covid-19 Abstract (journals.lww.com)
		Jiayintan	79		2/2/2020	2/23/2020	Consecutively conf. discharged pts	Clinical characteristics of non-ICU hospitalized patients with coronavirus disease 2019 and liver injury: A retrospective study
		Jiayintan	55		1/17/2020	2/25/2020	All severe patients within window	
		Xiaohou People's Hospital	28	11	1/31/2020	3/17/2020	28 Severe & Critically ill patients	Clinical analysis of severe COVID-19 patients
		Reunion Hospital [Wu U]	25	25	1/4/2020	2/13/2020	25 Deaths at Reunion	Clinical characteristics of 25 death cases with COVID-19: A retrospective review of medical records in a single medical center, Wuhan, China
		Union Jiangbei	33					Clinical features of 162 fatal cases of COVID-19: a multi-center retrospective study
		Wuhan 7th	31					Clinical features of 162 fatal cases of COVID-19: a multi-center retrospective study
		Wuhan 7th	233					Clinical features of 162 fatal cases of COVID-19: a multi-center retrospective study
		Wuhan 1 mg	56	8	12/29/2019	1/31/2020	discharged or died by 1/31/2020; 813 adult patients	An Advanced Study of Urban Emergency Medical Equipment Logistics Distribution for Different Levels of Urgency Demand
		Wuhan Central	443	40	12/25/2019	2/15/2020		Hospitalization and Critical Care of 109 Decedents with COVID-19 Pneumonia in Wuhan, China
		Zhongshan Hospital	1524		12/30/2019	2/17/2020		SARS-CoV-2 Transmission in Patients With Cancer at a Tertiary Care Hospital in Wuhan, China Global Health JAMA Network
		Zhongshan Fangcang	190	5	2/15/2020	3/8/2020	100 Pts infected 150 family members	Investigation of 100 SARS-CoV-2 infected families in Wuhan: Transmission patterns and follow-up

All of the data included within this analysis comes from peer-reviewed, censor-approved sources

All 65 Epidemiological Studies/Sources Compiled for this Analysis - The 38 Unique Sources for the Main list are highlighted in [Purple]

Wuhan COVID-19 Outbreak - Case & Death Data Source Study [with active link]		Country & Author Background information			
		Country	City/Pr	District	Hospital/Org
1	[protected, pending publication]	China	Wuhan		
2	1-year outcomes in hospital survivors with COVID-19: a longitudinal cohort study	China	Wuhan	Dongxihu	Jiayintan
3	A comparative analysis of clinical characteristics in patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 between Wuhan and Zhoushan, China	China	Zhoushan		
4	A cross-sectional comparison of epidemiological and clinical features of patients with coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in Wuhan and outside Wuhan, China	China*	Guangzhou		
5	An Advanced Study of Urban Emergency Medical Equipment Logistics Distribution for Different Levels of Urgency Demand	China	Xi'an		
6	Analysis of 92 deceased patients with COVID-19	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Renmin
7	Analysis of clinical characteristics and laboratory findings of 95 cases of 2019 novel coronavirus pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a retrospective analysis	China	Wuhan	Xinshou	People's Hospital
8	Analysis of clinical features of COVID-19 in cancer patients	China	Wuhan	Qisokou	Wuhan No. 1
9	Analysis of the Risk Factors for Mortality in Adult COVID-19 Patients in Wuhan: A Multicenter Study	China	Wuhan	Wuchang*	Zhongnans*
10	Association of D-dimer elevation with inflammation and organ dysfunction in ICU patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a retrospective observational study	China	Wuhan*	Dongxihu	Jiayintan
11	Benefits from Shortening Viral Shedding by Traditional Chinese Medicine Treatment for Moderate COVID-19: An Observational Study	China	Wuhan	Jiangxiu	Fangcang
12	Case analysis of novel coronavirus pneumonia in the Second Hospital of Wuhan Iron and Steel Company, Qingshan District, Wuhan, China	China	Tianjin		
13	Characteristics of 1738 Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan	Dongxihu	Fangcang
14	Clinical analysis of severe COVID-19 patients	China	Qinghai		
15	Clinical and Laboratory Predictors of In-hospital Mortality in Patients With Coronavirus Disease-2019: A Cohort Study in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan	Qisokou	Tongji Union
16	Clinical characteristics and analysis of risk factors for disease progression of COVID-19: A retrospective Cohort Study	China	Beijing		
17	Clinical characteristics and co-infections of 354 hospitalized patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a retrospective cohort study - ScienceDirect	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Renmin
18	Clinical characteristics and outcomes of COVID-19 patients with gastrointestinal symptoms admitted to Jiangnan Fangcang Shelter Hospital in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan	Qisokou	Tongji Union
19	Clinical characteristics and prognostic factors of COVID-19 patients progression to severe: a retrospective, observational study	China	Wuhan	Qisokou	Tongji Union
20	Clinical Characteristics of 138 Hospitalized Patients With 2019 Novel Coronavirus-Infected Pneumonia in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Zhongnan
21	Clinical characteristics of 141 deaths from novel coronavirus pneumonia in Wuhan, Jinwintan Hospital	China	Changsha		
22	Clinical characteristics of 25 death cases with COVID-19: A retrospective review of medical records in a single medical center, Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Renmin
23	Clinical characteristics of 30 COVID-19 patients with epilepsy: A retrospective study in Wuhan	China	Wuhan	Jiang'an	Wuhan Central
24	Clinical characteristics of 70 fatal patients with COVID-19	China	Wuhan	Qisokou	Tongji
25	Clinical characteristics of non-ICU hospitalized patients with coronavirus disease 2019 and liver injury: A retrospective study	China	Fuzhou		
26	Clinical Characteristics of Nutritional Indicators in Patients with Covid-19	China	Hebei		
27	Clinical Features and CT Imaging Analysis of 76 Patients with Corona Virus Disease 暨南大学学报(自然科学与医学版), 2020.	China	Lanzhou		
28	Clinical features and mortality factors of severe novel coronavirus pneumonia	China	Wuhan	Jiangnan	Jiangnan University
29	Clinical features of 162 fatal cases of COVID-19: a multi-center retrospective study	China	Wuhan	3 Districts	5 Hospitals
30	Clinical outcomes of COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a large cohort study	China	Shanghai		
31	COVID-19 Is Distinct From SARS-CoV-2-Negative Community-Acquired Pneumonia	China	Wuhan*	Jiangnan	Red Cross
32	COVID-19-associated coagulopathy: thromboembolism prophylaxis and poor prognosis in ICU	China	Guangzhou		
33	Critically Ill Patients with Coronavirus Disease 2019 in a Designated Hospital in Wuhan	China	Wuhan	Qisokou	Tongji
34	Death from Covid-19 of 23 Health Care Workers in China	China*			
35	Deep learning-based triage and analysis of lesion burden for COVID-19: a retrospective study with external validation	China	Wuhan	Qisokou	Tongji
36	Determinants of mortality of patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a case-control study	China	Shanghai		
37	Development and Validation of a Prognostic Risk Score System for COVID-19 Inpatients: A Multi-Center Retrospective Study in China	China*	Wuhan*	Qisokou*	Tongji
38	Diagnosis and treatment of 471 patients with 2019 novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19)	China	Shanghai		
39	Elderly Male With Cardiovascular-Related Comorbidities Has a Higher Rate of Fatal Outcomes: A Retrospective Study in 602 Patients With COVID-19	China	Wuhan*	Jiang'an	Hankou Hospital
40	Epidemiologic Characteristics of and Prognostic Factors for COVID-19 Among Hospitalized Patients: Updated Implications From Hubei Province, China	China	Wuhan	Hongshan	Hubei Maternal/Child
41	Epidemiological and clinical characteristics of 99 cases of 2019 novel coronavirus pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a descriptive study	China	Wuhan	Dongxihu	Jiayintan
42	Factors Defining the Development of Severe Illness in Patients with COVID-19: A Retrospective Study	China	Beijing		
43	Follow-up results of 117 patients with novel coronavirus pneumonia after discharge from Wuhan Fangcang Hospital	China	Wuhan	Hongshan	Hubei Cancer Hospital
44	Geographical and Epidemiological Characteristics of 3,487 Confirmed Cases With COVID-19 Among Healthcare Workers in China	China	Wuhan	Qisokou*	Tongji*
45	Hospitalization and Critical Care of 109 Decedents with COVID-19 Pneumonia in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan*	3 Districts	3 Hospitals
46	Investigation of 100 SARS-CoV-2 infected families in Wuhan: Transmission patterns and follow-up	China	Multiple		
47	Neurological Implications of Non-critically Ill Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 in a Fangcang Shelter Hospital in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Zhongnan
48	Predicting Progression of COVID-19 Infection to Prioritize Medical Resource Allocation: A Novel Triage Model Based on Patient Char. & Symptoms at Presentation	China*	Wuhan*	Wuchang	Zhongnan
49	Regional Differences in Epidemiological & Clinical Characteristics, Treatment, and Clinical Outcomes of COVID-19 in Wuhan and Remote Areas of Hubei Province	China*	Wuhan*	Wuchang*	Renmin*
50	Retrospective analysis of clinical features in 134 coronavirus disease 2019 cases	China	Hefei		
51	Risk Factors Associated With Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome and Death in Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 Pneumonia in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan*	Dongxihu	Jiayintan
52	SARS-CoV-2 Transmission in Patients With Cancer at a Tertiary Care Hospital in Wuhan, China	China*	Wuhan	Wuchang	Zhongnan
53	Sex differences in clinical characteristics and risk factors for mortality among severe patients with COVID-19: a retrospective study	China	Wuhan*	Wuchang	Renmin
54	The characteristics and death risk factors of 132 COVID-19 pneumonia patients with comorbidities: a retrospective single-center analysis in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan	Qisokou	Wuhan No. 1; Hubei 3rd
55	The health & economic impact of constructing temp. field hospitals to meet the COVID-19 pandemic surge: Wuhan Leishenshan Hospital in China as a case study	China*	Wuhan	Wuchang	Zhongnan
56	The incidence, risk factors and prognosis of acute kidney injury in severe and critically ill patients with COVID-19 in mainland China: a retrospective study	China	Guangzhou		
57	The paradoxical problem with COVID-19 ocular infection: Moderate clinical manifestation and potential infection risk	China	Wuhan*	Caidian*	Huoshenchan*
58	The worldwide COVID-19 outbreak: Advice and recommendation on radiology mgmt & infection control from makeshift hospitals in Wuhan	China	Jilin		
59	Thrombocytopenia and its association with mortality in patients with COVID-19	China	Wuhan	Qisokou*	Tongji Union
60	Tobacco smoking confers risk for severe COVID-19 unexplainable by pulmonary imaging	China	Wuhan	Jiangnan	Red Cross*
61	Treatment efficacy analysis of traditional Chinese medicine for novel coronavirus pneumonia (COVID-19): an empirical study from Wuhan, Hubei Province, China	China	Macao		
62	Wuchang Fangcang Shelter Hospital: Practices, Experiences, and Lessons Learned in Controlling COVID-19	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Renmin*
63	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226 - Usage of Beds in Wuhan Hospitals	China	Wuhan		
64	Spatiotemporal characteristics and factor analysis of SARS-CoV-2 infections among healthcare workers in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Wuhan University
65	Household transmission of SARS-CoV-2 during the Wuhan outbreak - Data for plotting maps in figure S1 - Wuhan sub-district case & transmission data	China*	Wuhan	Qisokou	Tongji

This data continues to be ignored by China, the WHO, intelligence agencies and scientists arguing in support of the Huanan Market hypothesis

Limitations & Considerations

A number of limitations and assumptions exist as a result of working with such a large and varied volume of data, but, given the size of the disparity between the ‘official’ data and what has been aggregated within this analysis, it is exceedingly improbable that any single one – or any combination – would be enough to negate the overall conclusions.

- This analysis does not include any overlap that may exist between the 3 ‘types’ of cases that have been included (health care worker [HCW], Fangcang and “all others”), as listed in the figure below. It is known that some of the Fangcang patients were ultimately transferred to a designated hospital when their condition progressed to a more severe or critical state; however, as explained in the next paragraph, this does not dramatically impact the overall distribution because the Fangcang shelter hospitals didn’t even begin operation until February, more than a week after the harsh lockdown measures were imposed.

	Cases			Deaths
	Counted	Expected	Δ Expected	
Fangcang	15,935	12,000	132.8%	74
Health-Care Workers [HCW]	3,051	3,058	99.8%	23
All other Confirmed/Diagnosed	33,702	37,022	91.0%	1,079
Total Cases	52,688	50,340	104.7%	1,176
Total Deaths	1,176	3,869	30.4%	
All Reported Cases in Wuhan:	53,864	54,209	99.4%	
	-345	-0.64%		

- Most studies do not explicitly mention whether or not HCW patients were included in their cohorts. There are also examples of HCW’s having never been officially included as cases, such

as the doctor [Lin Qingchuan] whose story is described in the first chapter of Murong Xuecun's book *Deadly Quiet City*.¹⁶

In considering the evidence and conclusions within this analysis, one should consider the context from which they have arisen. For example, it is highly unlikely that the geospatial distribution that is described above is the product of manipulation, especially when compared to the 'official' data from the Chinese NHC; *if* someone sought to manipulate data and results from dozens of individual cohort studies from dozens of academic and medical institutions in Wuhan and across China, it is highly unlikely that they would do so to produce a set of data that, when aggregated, provide strong evidence of manipulation. In addition, more than 95% of confirmed cases emerged *after* the unprecedented lockdown measures were put in place on the morning of January 23rd, 2020,¹⁷ which included the effective cessation of traffic across the mile-wide Yangtze River. As a result, the final West-East proportion of cases should approximately resemble the epidemiological picture as it stood when the lockdown measures were implemented.

Conclusion

These articles and their aggregated data deserve greater attention, so why haven't more scientists investigated the published literature which examines various aspects of the Wuhan outbreak? **China's disinterest in the research produced by its own scientists is unusual, because many possible outcomes could help exonerate the country from suspicions regarding the origin of the pandemic.**

The alternative is that China's silence is a natural result of being stuck in a corner, unable to offer any evidence that could clear their name because none exists. In other words, there would be little sense

¹⁶ Murong Xuecun, *Deadly Quiet City*, Hardie Grant Publishing (Sydney, Australia: 2022).

¹⁷ Ongoing coverage, "China coronavirus: Lockdown measures rise across Hubei province," *BBC News* (1/23/2020). <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-china-51217455>

in refusing to release non-personal treatment information if it clearly showed a pattern centered somewhere else [somewhere less suspicious].

Instead, the numbers reported to the WHO [after a year] were mere summaries of *China's* own internal investigation, with no raw data in support; the WHO was reduced to simply drawing conclusions from unverifiable data. This is equivalent to relying solely upon the defendant in a court case to provide the prosecution with the evidence that guilt must be extracted from – a presumption of innocence, however, doesn't negate a defendant's obligation to address evidence beyond that which they provide.

Furthermore, the unwillingness of scientific institutions and intelligence agencies *outside* of China to conduct analyses such as what has been described here is just as concerning; given the scale and impact of the COVID-19 pandemic upon humanity, the lack of due diligence applied in search of its origins is appalling regardless of whether the virus emerged from nature or from a lab in China or anywhere else.

~A note from the author:

As a member of DRASTIC, I have investigated the origins of the COVID-19 pandemic for one reason – to uncover the truth, for the sake of the victims, independent of any geopolitical considerations. This was the perspective from which I approached the release of the DEFUSE documents in September 2021, and it remains my perspective today.

περὶ δὲ τῆς ἀπορίας τῆς εἰρημένης περὶ τε τοὺς ὀρισμοὺς καὶ περὶ τοὺς ἀριθμοὺς, τί αἴτιον τοῦ ἔν εἶναι; πάντων γὰρ ὅσα πλείω μέρη ἔχει καὶ μὴ ἔστιν οἷον σωρὸς τὸ πᾶν ἄλλ'

-Aristotle, *Metaphysics* VIII, 1045a. 8-10

Appendix A: Aggregated Wuhan COVID-19 Case & Death Data

AGGREGATED CASE & DEATH DATA FOR THE WUHAN COVID-19 OUTBREAK

Data from 167 Hospitals, across 97 Sub-Districts, from Chinese Censor-Approved Sources

District	ADM	Hospital [Translated]	Tier	Cat	HCW Cx	Conf. Ptnts	Dx
Wuchang	42010602	Renmin Hospital [Wu U]	3 A	Gen	205	5,510	147
Qiaokou	42010405	Tongji	3 A	Gen	156	2,977	70
Dongxihu	42011214	Jinyintan	3 A	Inf D	21	2,469	238
Hongshan	42011103	Hubei Maternal/Child [Opt. Valley]	3 A	Comm	16	1,765	32
Jiang'an	42010202	Wuhan Central	3 A	Gen	293	1,550	40
Qiaokou	42010406	Wuhan 1st Hospital	3 A	Gen	102	1,476	
Hongshan	42011102	Wuhan 3rd [Gaunggu]	3 A	Gen	4	1,241	70
Wuchang	42010612	Zhongnan [Wu U]	3 A	Gen	98	1,181	30
Jianghan	42010307	Wuhan Red Cross	2 A	Gen	105	954	78
Jiang'an	42010207	Wuhan 6th	3 B	Gen	49	891	63
Jiangxia	42011518	Tongji Hospital [Optics Valley Branch]	3 A	Gen	3	825	
Hongshan		4th PLA General H [source pending release]	3 A	Gen		816	
Hongshan	42011102	Hubei People's/Provincial	3 A	TCM	40	794	
Jianghan	42010308	Wuhan Concord	3 A	Gen	91	791	
Hongshan	42011116	Hubei Cancer Hospital	3 A	Onco	6	761	
Jiang'an	42010212	Hankou Hospital	2 A	Gen	54	602	63
Dongxihu	42011201	Wuhan 4th [Changqing Branch]	1 A	Comm	1	569	
Hanyang	42010507	Wuhan 5th	3 A	Gen	79	500	
Wuchang	42010610	Wuchang Hospital	3 A	Gen	34	481	
Qiaokou	42010409	Hubei 3rd People's	3 A	Gen	116	459	13
Huangpi	42011601	Huangpi TCM	3 A	TCM	10	442	
Hanyang	42010511	Wuhan Yaxin Hospital	3 A	Gen	28	440	
Qingshan	42010710	Wuhan 9th Hospital	2 A	Gen	17	408	
Jiang'an	42010209	Hubei TCM	3 A	Gen	40	371	
Hanyang	42010502	Hanyang Hospital - W/TCM	3 B	Gen	43	366	
Wuchang	42010602	Wuhan Tianyou	3 A	Gen	11	362	29
Hongshan	42011103	Hongshan TCM	3 A	TCM	6	344	
Wuchang	42010603	Wuhan 3rd [Shouyi]	3 A	Gen	89	334	26
Caidian	42011401	Caidian Maternity Hospital [Xintian]	2 B	Comm	3	333	
Hongshan	42011104	Hubei 672	3 A	Ortho	7	305	
Wuchang	42010612	Wuhan 7th	2 A	Gen	69	297	51
Jiangxia	42011501	Jiangxia 1st People's	3 A	Gen	44	296	22
Hongshan	42011110	Wuhan Lung [Pulm.]	3 B	Inf D	12	273	45
Xinzhou	42011701	Xinzhou TCM	2 A	TCM	2	267	
Jiangxia	42011504	Jiangxia TCM	2 A	TCM	52	250	
Dongxihu	42011217	Wuhan Taikang	2 A	Gen	7	246	
Wuchang	42010609	Wuhan Bauhanian	3 A	Gen	9	238	
Jiang'an	42010208	Wuhan 8th	2 A	Gen	47	216	
Jiang'an	42010207	Wuhan Children's Hospital	3 A	Gen	30	191	
Jiang'an	42010213	Yangtze River Shipping General Hospital	3 B	Gen	82	153	
Hannan	42011308	Hannan Peoples' Hospital	2 B	Gen	6	153	
Qingshan	42010709	WISCO 2nd Staff Hospital	3 B	Gen	79	146	7
Xinzhou	42011701	Xinzhou Peoples' Hospital	2 A	Gen	3	130	11
Qiaokou	42010415	Wuhan 4th Hospital	3 A	Gen	115	102	3

Qingshan	42010702	Wugang General Hospital	3 A	Gen	99	100	
Dongxihu	42011212	Wuhan Union Peoples' Hospital - West	3 B	Gen	19	79	
Qingshan	42010701	Wuhan Puren Hospital	3 A	Gen	58	76	
Hongshan	42011107	Wuhan Pear Garden	3 A	Gen	39	59	
Caidian	42011411	Caidian Branch [Tongji]	2 A	Gen	15	59	41
Caidian	42011401	Wuhan Jihe [W/TCM]	2 A	Comm	1	54	
Jianghan	42010306	Wuhan Asian Heart Hospital	3 A	Heart	75		
Jianghan	42010311	Center Hospital Back Lake Hospital	3 A	Gen	35		
Huangpi	42011601	Huangxuan People's Hospital	3 B	Gen	32		
Jiang'an	42010209	Wuhan Mental Health Center	3 A	Psych	30		
Jiang'an	42010203	Wuhan TCM Hospital	3 A	TCM	27		
Jianghan	42010307	Wuhan Commercial Hospital	2 A	Comm	23		
Jianghan	42010311	Wuhan Jimin Hospital for the Elderly	2 A	Comm	18		
Hongshan	42011116	Rongjun Hospital, Hubei Prv	2 A	Gen	17		
Jianghan	42010311	Wuhan Yufu Hospital	2 A	Gen	17		
Qiaokou	42010403	Han Jiaxuan St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm	15		
Qiaokou	42010416	Gutian St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm	11		
Dongxihu	42011214	2nd People's Hospital of East-West Lake	2 A	Gen	10		
Jiang'an	42010213	Taipei St CHSC, Riverside	1 A	Comm	10		
Qiaokou	42010403	Wuhan Renai Hospital	2 A	Gen	10		
Hongshan	42011102	Wuhan Changying Hospital	2 A	Gen	9		
Wuchang	42010612	Hubei Prv directly under the organ hospital	2 A	Gen	9		
Hanyang	42010509	Qinkou St CHSC, Hanyang	1 A	Comm	7		
Qiaokou	42010405	Baofeng St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm	7		
Jiangxia	42011501	Paper House Health Hospital, Jiangxia	1 A	Comm	6		
Qiaokou	42010405	Wuhan Women's Prison Hospital, Hubei Prv	2 B	Comm	6		
Hongshan	42011102	CHSC of Huazhong Ag U, Lion Mountain St	1 A	Comm	5		
Qingshan	42010704	Red Steel City St CHSC in Qingshan	1 A	Comm	5		
Hongshan	42011116	Zhuo Daoquan St CHC in Hongshan	1 A	Comm	4		
Jiang'an	42010214	The CHSC of Yanjiaji St in Jiangjiang	1 A	Comm	4		
Qiaokou	42010403	Zongguan St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm	4		
Qiaokou	42010406	Ronghua St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm	4		
Qiaokou	42010409	Hanzhong St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm	4		
Dongxihu	42011203	Wuhan E-W L to walk Maling St CHH	1 A	Comm	3		
Hongshan	42011105	Zhangjiawan St CHSC in Hongshan	1 A	Comm	3		
Huangpi	42011601	Qianchuan St HH, Huangxuan	1 A	Comm	3		
Huangpi	42011606	Magnolia Township HH in Huangxian	1 A	Comm	3		
Jiang'an	42010207	Labor St CHSC, Riverside	1 A	Comm	3		
Jiang'an	42010211	CHSC, North Stadium St, Jiangjiang	1 A	Comm	3		
Jianghan	42010305	Public Opinion St CHSC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm	3		
Wuchang	42010603	Wuchang CDC, Wuhan	1 A	Comm	3		
Wuchang	42010603	Wuchang Wuhan, First Yilu St CHSC	1 A	Comm	3		
Wuchang	42010611	Garden Mtn Hospital Area, Hubei Central	3 A	TCM	3		
Caidian	42011402	Dwarf St Health Hospital in Caidian	1 A	Comm	2		
Caidian	42011407	Park Tree Village HR on Yong'an St, Caidian	1 A	Comm	2		
Dongxihu	42011212	Jinyin Lake St HH in E-W Lake	1 A	Comm	2		
Hanyang	42010508	2nd Bridge St CHSC, Hanyang	1 A	Comm	2		
Huangpi	42011601	Wuhan Huangpu W/TCM & Maternity H	2 A	Gen	2		
Huangpi	42011605	Wangjiahe St Health Hospital, Huangxian	1 A	Comm	2		
Huangpi	42011613	Tianhe HH, Huangxian	1 A	Comm	2		
Huangpi	42011618	Huangxuan People's H (Panlong Branch)	3 B	Gen	2		
Jiang'an	42010208	Yongqing St CHSC, Jiangjiang	1 A	Comm	2		
Jiang'an	42010210	Hubei Provincial Armed Police Hq Hospital	3 A	Gen	2		

Jiang'an	42010217	Yangtze River Water Resources Commission H	2 B	Comm	2
Jiang'an	42010218	Wuhan Hongji Orthopaedic Hospital	3 A	Ortho	2
Jianghan	42010301	Manchun St CHSC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm	2
Jianghan	42010302	CHSC of Civil Rights St, Jianghan	1 A	Comm	2
Jianghan	42010313	Evergreen St CHSC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm	2
Jiangxia	42011501	Women's & Children's HH in Jiangxia	1 A	Comm	2
Jiangxia	42011504	Health Hospital, Jiangxia	1 A	Comm	2
Jiangxia	42011517	Tibetan Long Island CHSC in Jiangxia	1 A	Comm	2
Qingshan	42010701	Puren riverbank Hospital	2 A	Gen	2
Wuchang	42010607	Yuqiao St CHSC, Wuchang	1 A	Comm	2
Wuchang	42010613	Hubei Geological Staff Hospital	2 B	Comm	2
Caidian	42011406	Daji St Health Hospital in Caidian	1 A	Comm	1
Caidian	42011409	Military Hill St Health Hospital, Wuhan EDZ	1 A	Comm	1
Dongxihu	42011208	Xin'andu St Health Hospital, E-W Lake	1 A	Comm	1
Dongxihu	42011210	ParkQuan St Health Hospital, E-W Lake	1 A	Comm	1
Dongxihu	42011211	Weihe St Health Hospital in E-W Lake	1 A	Comm	1
Dongxihu	42011215	Wuhan East-West Lake Trail River St Health H	1 A	Comm	1
Hanyang	42010507	Wansong St CHSC, Hanjiang	1 A	Comm	1
Hanyang	42010507	Jianqiao St CHSC, Hanyang	1 A	Comm	1
Hongshan	42011102	Changying CHSC on Guanshan St, Hongshan	1 A	Comm	1
Hongshan	42011103	Wang Bingxi Medical Clinic in Hongshan	1 A	Comm	1
Hongshan	42011104	CHSC, Central Agricultural U of China	1 A	Comm	1
Hongshan	42011104	China Construction Bureau Wuhan Central H	2 B	Gen	1
Hongshan	42011105	Zhangjiawan St Guangxia CHSS in Hongshan	1 A	Comm	1
Hongshan	42011107	Pear Garden CHSC,	1 A	Comm	1
Hongshan	42011108	Wuhan Fangtai Hospital	2 A	Gen	1
Hongshan	42011112	Wuhan East Lake H-T DZ Buddha Zuling CSC	1 A	Comm	1
Hongshan	42011112	Zuoling St HSC, East Lake H-T DZ	1 A	Comm	1
Hongshan	42011114	Huashan St CHSC, East Lake H-T DZ	1 A	Comm	1
Hongshan	42011114	Huashan St CHSC, East Lake H-T DZ	1 A	Comm	1
Hongshan	42011117	Wuhan HouDekang Hospital	2 B	Comm	1
Hongshan	42011117	2nd CHSC of East Lake Eco-SA	1 A	Comm	1
Hongshan	42011119	Wuhan E-L H-T DZ Kanto St Longcheng CHSC	1 A	Comm	1
Huangpi	42011601	Women's & Children's HH in Huangxian	1 A	Comm	1
Huangpi	42011601	CHSC of Qianchuan St Ring City in Huangxuan	1 A	Comm	1
Huangpi	42011603	Yaojiaji St HH in Huangxian	1 A	Comm	1
Huangpi	42011612	Hengdian St CHH, Huangxian	1 A	Comm	1
Huangpi	42011616	Wuhan Huangxuan Sanliqiao St HH	1 A	Comm	1
Huangpi	42011616	HR, Deng Wei Village, Sanliqiao St, Huangxuan	1 A	Comm	1
Jiang'an	42010206	Xima St CHSC, Riverside	1 A	Comm	1
Jiang'an	42010207	Zhaojia-bin CHSC, Labor St, Jiangjiang	1 A	Comm	1
Jiang'an	42010212	Wuhan Lushan Hospital	1 A	Comm	1
Jiang'an	42010212	Danshui Pool St CHSC, Wuhan Riverside	1 A	Comm	1
Jiang'an	42010219	Tazihu St CHSC, Riverside	1 A	Comm	1
Jianghan	42010306	Wuhan 1st Oral Hospital	3 B	Oral	1
Jianghan	42010306	Forward St CHSC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm	1
Jianghan	42010307	CHSC of National St, Jianghan	1 A	Comm	1
Jianghan	42010308	Wuhan Emergency Center	1 A	Comm	1
Jianghan	42010308	Xinhua St CHSC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm	1
Jianghan	42010309	Wansong St CHSC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm	1
Jianghan	42010309	Wansong St CHC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm	1
Jianghan	42010310	CDC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm	1

Jiangnan	42010313	Chang II CHSS, Hanxing St CHSC, Jiangnan	1 A	Comm	1
Jiangxia	42011501	CDC, Jiangxia	1 A	Comm	1
Jiangxia	42011504	Wulongquan HH Land Branch, Jiangxia	B	Comm	1
Jiangxia	42011513	CHSC of Bridge New Area, Jiangxia EDZ	1 A	Comm	1
Qiaokou	42010403	3604 Hospital	3 A	Gen	1
Qiaokou	42010404	Hanshuiqiao St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm	1
Qiaokou	42010414	Changfeng St CSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm	1
Qiaokou	42010415	Wuhan Puai Hospital	3 A	Gen	1
Qingshan	42010703	Xingouqiao St CHSC, Qingshan	1 A	Comm	1
Qingshan	42010707	Wuhan Qingshan Factory Front St CHSC	1 A	Comm	1
Qingshan	42010708	Wudong Hospital	2 A	Psych	1
Wuchang	42010601	Baishazhou St CHSC, Wuchang	1 A	Comm	1
Wuchang	42010610	2nd CHSC on Yangyuan St, Wuchang	1 A	Comm	1
Wuchang	42010610	Wuhan U of Technology CHSC, Yangyuan St	1 A	Comm	1
Wuchang	42010611	South Lake CHSC, Zhongnan Road St	1 A	Comm	1
Wuchang	42010613	Wuhan Wupan Hospital	2 B	Gen	1
Xinzhou	42011701	Xinzhou Lucheng Health Service Center	1 A	Comm	1
Xinzhou	42011713	Yanglu Central Hospital, Hubei Prv	2 A	Gen	1
Xinzhou	42011713	Yanglu CHSC, Xinzhou	1 A	Comm	1

Appendix B: Wuhan CDC Update 20200226 – Hospital Bed Usage in Wuhan

Wuhan CDC Update 20200226 - Usage of Beds in Designated Hospitals								
Hospital name	Peak		Used			Empty		
			14th	15th	16th	14th	15th	16th
1 Jinyintan	822	Dongxihu	793	822	811	0	0	0
2 Wuhan Lung Hospital	160	Hongshan	142	133	160	0	0	0
3 Hankou Hospital	389	Jiang'an	368	389	376	10	0	2
4 Wuchang Hospital	481	Wuchang	479	471	481	25	33	23
5 Wuhan 5th	500	Hanyang	500	495	487	0	0	0
6 Wuhan 7th	297	Wuchang	276	297	288	0	0	0
7 Wuhan 9th	408	Qingshan	400	408	403	5	0	2
8 Red Cross	350	Jiangnan	348	342	350	22	28	50
9 Wuhan 4th (West Branch)	569	Dongxihu	407	524	569	74	31	50
10 WISCO Staff Hospital	146	Qingshan	146	145	139	21	22	13
11 Wuhan Central	595	Jiang'an	562	595	577	0	0	0
12 Wuhan 3rd (Optics Valley Branch)	616	Hongshan	474	616	616	126	0	0
13 Tongji Hospital	1,048	Qiaokou	1,047	1,048	1,047	3	2	3
14 Tongji Union - Concord	791	Jiangnan	791	791	778	0	0	32
15 Hubei People's Hospital (East)	794	Hongshan	794	772	774	6	28	26
16 Hubei W/TCM	371	Jiangnan	360	350	371	33	43	22
17 Tianyou Hospital	362	Wuchang	309	358	362	0	0	0
18 Wuhan 6th	485	Jiang'an	463	476	485	37	24	15
19 Wuhan TCM [Hanyang Branch]	366	Hanyang	283	297	366	0	0	0
20 Hubei 672 Ortho W/TCM	305	Hongshan	305	298	299	0	0	6
21 Huangpi TCM	384	Huangpi	383	384	382	28	27	29
22 Jiangxia TCM	250	Jiangxia	250	236	231	0	0	0
23 Xinzhou TCM	267	Jiangxia	264	267	261	0	0	39
24 Wuhan Bauhinia	238	Wuchang	238	237	237	50	51	51
25 Hannan TCM	23	Hannan	19	10	23	7	16	3
26 Caidian Mother & Child	333	Caidian	333	328	328	20	25	25
27 PLA Hospital	283	Wuchang	281	283	280	0	0	0
28 Houshenshan [FangCang]	1,014	Caidian	1,014	1,014	1,010	0	0	0
29 Leishenshan [FangCang]	567	Jiangxia	483	473	567	0	0	0
30 Wuhan Children's Hospital	191	Jiangnan	190	191	191	36	35	35
31 Tongji Hospital (Optics Valley Brar	825	Hongshan	809	811	825	19	17	3
32 Wuhan 8th	216	Jiang'an	212	216	182	47	43	55
33 Wuhan New Town Hospital	94		93	94	94	0	0	0
34 Hubei 3rd People's Hospital [Yang	130	Xinzhou	120	127	130	15	8	5
35 Wuhan Yaxin	440	Hanyang	438	440	438	12	14	13
36 Wuhan 1st	1,052	Qiaokou	629	1,052	1,052	213	90	90
37 Hubei TCM (Optics Valley Branch)	344	Hongshan	300	344	336	14	0	0
38 Taikang Hospital	246	Dongxihu	143	143	246	57	57	114
39 Tongji Union Cancer Hospital	761	Hongshan	0	493	761	0	83	47
40 Hubei 3rd People's Hospital	113	Qiaokou	0	113	110	0	0	0
41 WISCO General Hospital	100	Qingshan	0	100	91	0	0	0
42 Wuhan Nursing Hospital	99		0	99	99	0	1	1
43 Wuhan Central (Main)	59	Jiang'an	0	0	59	0	0	0
44 Wuhan 3rd	155	Wuchang	0	0	155	0	0	445
45 Yangtze River Shipping GH	153	Jiang'an	0	0	153	0	0	0
46 Pear Garden Hospital	57	Wuchang	0	0	57	0	0	13
			15,446	17,082	18,037	880	678	1,212

Appendix C: Case & Death Data for the Fangcang Temporary/Shelter Hospitals

District	Fangcang Shelter Hospitals	Cx	Dx	St	End
Caidian	Huoshenshan Fangcang¹⁸	3,059	69	2/3	4/15
Jiangxia	Leishenshan Fangcang¹⁹	2,011		2/8	4/15
Hanyang	Hanjiang Fangcang²⁰	1,848		2/11	3/10
Jiangnan	Jiangnan Fangcang²¹	1,828		2/5	3/9
Dongxihu	Dongxihu Fangcang²²	1,738		2/7	2/26
Hongshan	East Lake-West Lake Fangcang²³	1,682		2/4	3/10
Wuchang	Wuchang Fangcang	1,124			
Wuchang	Zhuankou Fangcang²⁴	1,000	5	2/17	3/8
Hongshan	Guanggu Fangcang²⁵	722		2/21	3/6
Jiang'an	Jiang'an Fangcang²⁶	409			
Hanyang	Hanyang SS Fangcang²⁷	300		2/11	3/10
Hongshan	Hongshan Fangcang²⁸	117		2/2	3/6
Jiangxia	Dahuashan Fangcang²⁹	97			
Qiaokou	Qiaokou Wuti Fangcang	-			
Qiaokou	Wuhan Stadium Fangcang	-			
Hannan	Hannan Fangcang	-			
Huangpi	Huangpi Fangcang	-			
Qingshan	Qingshan Fangcang	-			

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<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fneur.2020.00895/full>

²⁴ Urianhkai Horchinbilig et al, "Investigation of 100 SARS-CoV-2 infected families in Wuhan: Transmission patterns and follow-up", *Journal of Global Health* (10/23/2020). <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7719352/>

²⁵ Minghuan Wang et al, "Deep learning-based triage and analysis of lesion burden for COVID-19: a retrospective study with external validation", *The Lancet Digital Health* (10/1/2020). [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/landig/article/PIIS2589-7500\(20\)30199-0/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/landig/article/PIIS2589-7500(20)30199-0/fulltext)

²⁶ Zhengtong Lv et al, "Clinical characteristics and analysis of risk factors for disease progression of COVID-19: A retrospective Cohort Study", *International Journal of Biological Sciences* (1/1/2021). <https://www.ijbs.com/v17p0001.htm>

²⁷ Mu Lin et al, "The worldwide coronavirus disease 2019 outbreak: Advice and recommendation on radiology management and infection control from makeshift hospitals in Wuhan", *Medicine* (5/14/2021). https://journals.lww.com/md-journal/Fulltext/2021/05140/The_worldwide_coronavirus_disease_2019_outbreak_4.aspx

²⁸ Zheng Yanlei et al, "Follow-up results of 117 patients with novel coronavirus pneumonia after discharge from Wuhan Fangcang Hospital", *Chinese Critical Care Emergency Management* (11/28/2020).

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²⁹ Qiliang Zhao et al, "Benefits from Shortening Viral Shedding by Traditional Chinese Medicine Treatment for Moderate COVID-19: An Observational Study", *Evidence-Based Complementary & Alternative Medicine* (2/1/2022).

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Appendix D: Sub-District Case Data – from “Household Transmission of SARS-CoV-2 during the Wuhan Outbreak”³⁰

*Data for plotting maps in figure S1 - Wuhan sub-district case & transmission data

**jiedao* populations extrapolated from the attack rate

ADM	District	Sub-District	Sub-District [trans]	Conf Cases	Atk R%	# of HH	C/HH	Sec. Atk	Pop
42010202	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区一元街道	One Yuan Street	327	0.95%	118	2.77	14.16	34,257
42010203	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区大智街道	Dazhi Street	349	0.98%	147	2.37	17.31	35,651
42010204	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区车站街道	Station Street	228	0.45%	100	2.28	15.70	50,801
42010205	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区四唯街道	Four Streets	199	0.58%	131	1.52	20.92	34,346
42010206	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区西马街道	Xima Street	583	0.88%	266	2.19	14.55	66,130
42010207	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区劳动街道	Labor Street	320	0.37%	156	2.05	18.71	87,414
42010208	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区永清街道	Yongqing Street	266	0.74%	112	2.38	17.30	36,164
42010209	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区二七街道	27th Street	586	0.67%	232	2.53	14.15	87,021
42010210	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区新村街道	New Village St	130	0.20%	87	1.49	15.84	65,087
42010211	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区球场街道	Riverside Court St	290	0.93%	152	1.91	23.72	31,138
42010212	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区丹水池街道	Dan Pool Street	279	0.43%	155	1.80	6.81	64,552
42010213	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区台北街道	Taipei Street	336	0.82%	161	2.09	22.99	41,055
42010214	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区谕家矶街道	Yanjiaji Street	84	0.27%	40	2.10	13.33	31,189
42010215	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区后湖街道	Back Lake Street	1,120	1.33%	517	2.17	14.34	83,899
42010217	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区花桥街道	Huaqiao Street	659	0.61%	335	1.97	14.52	107,757
42010218	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区百步亭社	CMC 100-Step Pav	427	0.75%	206	2.07	16.92	56,999
42010219	Riverside	湖北省武汉市江岸区塔子湖街道	Tazi Lake Street	520	1.06%	350	1.49	19.27	48,940
42010301	Jianghan	湖北省武汉市江汉区满春街道	Manchun Street	127	0.38%	70	1.81	25.20	33,453
42010302	Jianghan	湖北省武汉市江汉区民权街道	Civil Rights Street	244	0.35%	139	1.76	26.98	68,828
42010303	Jianghan	湖北省武汉市江汉区花楼水塔	Hualou W Tower St	304	0.78%	154	1.97	28.80	38,974
42010305	Jianghan	湖北省武汉市江汉区民意街道	Public Opinion St	364	0.91%	209	1.74	26.41	40,196
42010306	Jianghan	湖北省武汉市江汉区前进街道	Forward Street	184	0.48%	96	1.92	16.58	38,141
42010307	Jianghan	湖北省武汉市江汉区民族街道	Ethnic Street	161	0.47%	89	1.81	20.11	34,273
42010308	Jianghan	湖北省武汉市江汉区新华街道	Xinhua Street	314	0.59%	164	1.91	18.38	53,637
42010309	Jianghan	湖北省武汉市江汉区万松街道	Wansong Street	528	0.60%	285	1.85	20.34	88,350
42010310	Jianghan	湖北省武汉市江汉区北湖街道	North Lake Street	219	0.54%	124	1.77	14.10	40,184
42010311	Jianghan	湖北省武汉市江汉区唐家墩街道	Tang Jixuan Street	983	1.11%	489	2.01	17.22	88,321
42010312	Jianghan	湖北省武汉市江汉区汉兴街道	Hanxing Street	1,354	1.12%	734	1.84	19.91	120,881
42010313	Jianghan	湖北省武汉市江汉区常青街道	Evergreen Street	666	0.69%	300	2.22	17.41	96,240
42010401	Qiaokou	湖北省武汉市桥口区易家街道	Yijia Street	185	0.54%	96	1.93	24.22	34,438
42010402	Qiaokou	湖北省武汉市桥口区韩家墩街道	Han Jiakuan Street	542	0.52%	280	1.94	18.27	103,428
42010403	Qiaokou	湖北省武汉市桥口区宗关街道	Zongguan Street	375	0.48%	199	1.88	21.72	77,565
42010404	Qiaokou	湖北省武汉市桥口区汉水桥街道	Hanshuiqiao Street	717	0.97%	282	2.54	28.63	74,177
42010405	Qiaokou	湖北省武汉市桥口区宝丰街道	Baofeng Street	1,442	2.44%	343	4.20	28.14	59,075
42010406	Qiaokou	湖北省武汉市桥口区荣华街道	Ronghua Street	601	0.98%	289	2.08	30.43	61,404
42010407	Qiaokou	湖北省武汉市桥口区六角亭街道	Hexagon Street	364	0.75%	156	2.33	22.31	48,452
42010409	Qiaokou	湖北省武汉市桥口区汉申街道	Hanzhong Street	696	1.16%	316	2.20	22.32	60,251
42010414	Qiaokou	湖北省武汉市桥口区长丰街道	Changfeng Street	793	0.56%	397	2.00	23.29	140,683
42010415	Qiaokou	湖北省武汉市桥口区汉正街道	Hanzheng Street	737	0.62%	408	1.81	20.55	119,309
42010416	Qiaokou	湖北省武汉市桥口区古田街道	Gutian Street	691	0.77%	377	1.83	20.78	89,718
42010502	Hanyang	湖北省武汉市汉阳区建桥街道	Jianqiao Street	400	0.49%	264	1.52	18.02	81,203
42010503	Hanyang	湖北省武汉市汉阳区晴川街道	Qingchuan Street	154	0.49%	106	1.45	12.14	31,235
42010505	Hanyang	湖北省武汉市汉阳区鹦鹉街道	Parrot Street	560	0.96%	352	1.59	16.75	58,245
42010506	Hanyang	湖北省武汉市汉阳区洲头街道	Zhoutou Street	188	0.44%	135	1.39	18.18	42,535
42010507	Hanyang	湖北省武汉市汉阳区五里墩街道	Wuliyu Street	927	1.09%	600	1.55	19.03	85,038
42010508	Hanyang	湖北省武汉市汉阳区江汉二桥街	J'han 2 nd Bridge St	429	0.54%	271	1.58	17.00	79,180
42010509	Hanyang	湖北省武汉市汉阳区琴断口街道	Qinkou Street	544	0.50%	349	1.56	14.81	108,735
42010510	Hanyang	湖北省武汉市汉阳区永丰街道	Yongfeng Street	363	0.46%	263	1.38	21.12	79,245
42010511	Hanyang	湖北省武汉市汉阳区江堤街道	Jiangdi Street	713	1.49%	467	1.53	14.93	47,979
42010512	Hanyang	湖北省武汉市汉阳区四新街道	Four new streets	309	0.79%	208	1.49	15.93	39,305

³⁰ Fang Li et al, "Household transmission of SARS-CoV-2 and risk factors for susceptibility and infectivity in Wuhan: a retrospective observational study", *Lancet Infectious Diseases* (1/18/2021). <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33476567/>

42010513	Hanyang	湖北省武汉市汉阳区龙阳街道	Longyang Street	233	0.56%	136	1.71	16.15	41,596
42010601	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区白沙洲街道	Baishazhou Street	616	0.81%	326	1.89	15.41	76,226
42010602	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区紫阳街道	Ziyang Street	393	0.64%	180	2.18	17.72	61,135
42010603	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区首义路街道	First Yi Road Street	395	0.55%	179	2.21	12.04	71,652
42010604	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区黄鹤楼街道	Yellow Tower St	492	0.89%	195	2.52	20.52	55,207
42010605	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区中华路街道	China Road Street	228	0.52%	97	2.35	20.12	44,262
42010606	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区粮道街道	The food road st	424	0.66%	387	1.10	13.21	64,704
42010607	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区积玉桥街道	Yuqiao Street	424	0.58%	189	2.24	14.07	72,622
42010608	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区南湖街道	South Lake Street	399	0.66%	179	2.23	16.27	60,145
42010609	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区徐家棚街道	Xujiashan Street	908	0.79%	406	2.24	17.37	115,410
42010610	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区杨园街道	Yangyuan Street	768	0.64%	347	2.21	18.00	120,507
42010611	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区中南路街道	Zhongnan Road St	1,357	0.56%	602	2.25	18.72	242,114
42010612	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区水果湖街道	Fruit Lake Street	1,182	0.67%	496	2.38	13.95	175,890
42010613	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区珞珈山街道	Yujiashan Street	124	0.14%	49	2.53	10.58	87,234
42010614	Wuchang	湖北省武汉市武昌区石洞街道	Shidong Street	16	0.21%	4	4.00	0.00	7,620
42010701	Qingshan	湖北省武汉市青山区红卫路街道	Hongwei Road St	689	0.81%	437	1.58	17.68	84,795
42010702	Qingshan	湖北省武汉市青山区冶金街道	Metallurgical Street	377	0.46%	166	2.27	15.38	81,967
42010703	Qingshan	湖北省武汉市青山区新沟桥街道	Xingouqiao Street	174	0.30%	97	1.79	13.61	57,383
42010704	Qingshan	湖北省武汉市青山区红钢城街道	Red Steel City St	175	0.42%	92	1.90	25.00	41,523
42010705	Qingshan	湖北省武汉市青山区工人村街道	Qingshan W's V St	177	0.59%	119	1.49	9.81	29,921
42010706	Qingshan	湖北省武汉市青山区青山镇街道	Qingshan Town	100	0.30%	61	1.64	15.84	32,870
42010707	Qingshan	湖北省武汉市青山区厂前街道	Qingshan Factory St	40	0.30%	13	3.08	21.74	13,276
42010708	Qingshan	湖北省武汉市青山区武东街道	Wudong Street	123	0.49%	78	1.58	13.84	25,256
42010709	Qingshan	湖北省武汉市青山区白玉山街道	Baiyushan Street	111	0.27%	67	1.66	17.69	40,989
42010710	Qingshan	湖北省武汉市青山区钢花村街道	Steel Flower Vill St	659	0.82%	371	1.78	20.92	80,009
42010711	Qingshan	湖北省武汉市青山区化工新区	Bajifu Street	45	0.10%	34	1.32	9.17	44,500
42010712	Qingshan	湖北省武汉市青山区钢都管委会	Qingshan Steel MC	309	0.73%	172	1.80	21.02	42,511
42011102	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区关山街道	Guanshan Street	744	0.25%	437	1.70	21.38	296,086
42011103	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区珞南街道	Minnan Streets	581	0.28%	339	1.71	19.69	204,674
42011104	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区狮子山街道	Lion Mtn Street	553	0.41%	211	2.62	19.77	135,851
42011105	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区张家湾街道	Zhangjiawan Street	553	0.72%	341	1.62	22.68	76,364
42011107	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区梨园街道	Pear Garden Street	359	0.77%	203	1.77	17.30	46,472
42011108	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区洪山街道	Hongshan Street	594	0.64%	389	1.53	23.52	92,794
42011109	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区青菱街道	Qingling Street	152	0.12%	87	1.75	12.43	123,285
42011110	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区和平街道	Hongshan Peace St	1,027	1.48%	644	1.59	17.25	69,559
42011112	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区东湖高新区	Zuoling St [EL H-T]	181	0.33%	124	1.46	20.98	55,260
42011113	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区东湖高新区	Jiufeng St [EL-HT]	147	0.28%	96	1.53	18.03	52,788
42011114	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区东湖高	Huashan St [D H-T]	129	0.38%	96	1.34	19.33	34,240
42011115	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区天兴乡	Tianxing Township	13	0.32%	6	2.17	22.73	4,050
42011116	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区卓刀泉街道	Zhuo Daoquan St	461	0.38%	263	1.75	15.75	122,465
42011117	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区东湖风	Donghu Stts	493	0.58%	239	2.06	20.00	84,600
42011118	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区东湖高新	Donghu H-T Sts	525	0.47%	365	1.44	16.30	111,361
42011119	Hongshan	湖北省武汉市洪山区东湖高新	Kanto St [D H-T]	891	0.50%	542	1.64	23.45	178,200
42011201	Dongxihu	湖北省武汉市东西湖区长青街道	Changqing Street	136	0.29%	90	1.51	24.31	46,558
42011202	Dongxihu	湖北省武汉市东西湖区慈惠街道	Mercy St of City	38	0.22%	27	1.41	22.54	17,291
42011203	Dongxihu	湖北省武汉市东西湖区走马岭街	Maling Streets	26	0.08%	21	1.24	8.20	33,277
42011207	Dongxihu	湖北省武汉市东西湖区新沟镇街	Xingou Town St	43	0.17%	36	1.19	17.78	25,553
42011208	Dongxihu	湖北省武汉市东西湖区辛安渡街	Xin'andu Street	32	0.15%	25	1.28	13.83	20,946
42011209	Dongxihu	湖北省武汉市东西湖区东山街道	Dongshan Street	29	0.13%	24	1.21	7.27	22,647
42011210	Dongxihu	湖北省武汉市东西湖区柏泉街道	Baiquan Street	38	0.23%	31	1.23	21.31	16,413
42011211	Dongxihu	湖北省武汉市东西湖区径河街道	River Street	337	0.66%	251	1.34	19.08	51,132
42011212	Dongxihu	湖北省武汉市东西湖区金银湖街	Jinyin Lake Street	639	0.73%	447	1.43	19.67	87,870
42011214	Dongxihu	湖北省武汉市东西湖区将军路街	General Road St	433	0.68%	321	1.35	15.88	63,430
42011215	Dongxihu	湖北省武汉市东西湖区常青花园	Evergreen Gdn MC	343	0.52%	237	1.45	19.29	66,174
42011217	Dongxihu	湖北省武汉市东西湖区吴家山街	Wujiashan Street	450	0.40%	324	1.39	14.50	111,209
42011301	Hannan	湖北省武汉市汉南区湘口街道	Xiangkou Street	12	0.07%	8	1.50	6.67	16,700
42011303	Hannan	湖北省武汉市汉南区东荆街道	Dongjing Street	48	0.21%	29	1.66	3.85	23,200
42011306	Hannan	湖北省武汉市汉南区邓南街道	Dengnan Street	3	0.02%	1	3.00	0.00	16,700
42011308	Hannan	湖北省武汉市汉南区纱帽街道	Hat Street	195	0.52%	116	1.68	7.31	37,800
42011309	Hannan	湖北省武汉市汉南区沌口街道	Chaokou Street	445	0.33%	242	1.84	15.40	134,100
42011310	Hannan	湖北省武汉市汉南区沌阳街道	Chaoyang Street	355	0.49%	205	1.73	12.20	73,000

42011311	Hannan	湖北省武汉市汉南区军山街道	Junshan Street	88	0.25%	51	1.73	15.04	34,700
42011401	Caidian	湖北省武汉市蔡甸区蔡甸街道	Caidian Street	793	0.53%	540	1.47	14.41	150,325
42011402	Caidian	湖北省武汉市蔡甸区侏儒山街道	Gnome Mtn Street	72	0.15%	55	1.31	11.61	49,530
42011404	Caidian	湖北省武汉市蔡甸区索河街道	Sohe Street	36	0.13%	28	1.29	9.72	27,329
42011405	Caidian	湖北省武汉市蔡甸区张湾街道	Zhangwan Street	79	0.23%	61	1.30	12.87	33,873
42011406	Caidian	湖北省武汉市蔡甸区大集街道	Daji Street	136	0.37%	84	1.62	13.13	37,115
42011407	Caidian	湖北省武汉市蔡甸区永安街道	Yong'an Street	101	0.32%	69	1.46	14.55	31,198
42011408	Caidian	湖北省武汉市蔡甸区玉贤街道	Yuxian Street	34	0.19%	25	1.36	7.61	17,611
42011409	Caidian	湖北省武汉市蔡甸区黎山街道	Lushan Street	138	0.19%	103	1.34	12.87	73,205
42011410	Caidian	湖北省武汉市蔡甸区消泗乡	Caidian	23	0.12%	17	1.35	8.33	19,176
42011411	Caidian	湖北省武汉市蔡甸区桐湖办事处	The office of Luhu	10	0.33%	9	1.11	0.00	3,005
42011501	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区纸坊街道	Paper Square Str	377	0.22%	307	1.23	10.72	171,476
42011502	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区金口街道	Jinkou Street	56	0.07%	33	1.70	26.90	82,319
42011504	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区乌龙泉街道	Wulongquan Street	51	0.10%	43	1.19	9.43	49,014
42011505	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区郑店街道	Zhengdian Street	35	0.07%	32	1.09	1.04	47,474
42011507	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区五里界街道	Five-mile border st	14	0.06%	10	1.40	5.88	24,731
42011508	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区法泗街道	Fai Wei Streets	23	0.07%	19	1.21	5.10	32,785
42011509	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区安山街道	Anshan Street	10	0.03%	7	1.43	20.00	28,607
42011510	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区山坡街道	Hillside street	28	0.05%	18	1.56	21.52	59,238
42011511	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区湖泗街道	Huyi Street	17	0.05%	15	1.13	2.44	31,690
42011512	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区舒安街道	Shu'an Street	2	0.01%	2	1.00	5.56	20,454
42011513	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区大桥新区	Jiangxia Bridge NA	111	0.22%	89	1.25	11.98	49,749
42011514	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区金水办事处	Jinshui Office	3	0.02%	2	1.50	0.00	16,279
42011516	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区庙山开发区	Temple Mtn DZ	77	0.28%	54	1.43	12.80	27,674
42011517	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区藏龙岛开发	Tibetan Drag Isl DZ	103	0.22%	73	1.41	12.44	46,021
42011518	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区东湖高新区	Fuzuling Street	139	0.10%	66	2.11	23.42	143,500
42011519	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区东湖高新	Leopard Street	74	0.13%	47	1.57	14.41	55,464
42011520	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区东湖高新	Longquan Street	9	0.11%	7	1.29	0.00	8,212
42011521	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区东湖高新	Binhu Street	23	0.07%	14	1.64	8.33	34,792
42011523	Jiangxia	湖北省武汉市江夏区金港新区	Jingang New	7	0.08%	6	1.17	5.00	8,606
42011601	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区前川街道	Qianchuan Street	525	0.32%	354	1.48	14.54	164,963
42011602	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区蔡店街道	Caidian Street	52	0.16%	30	1.73	14.43	33,400
42011603	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区姚家集街道	Yaojiaji Street	73	0.14%	53	1.38	19.20	50,640
42011604	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区长轩岭街道	Chang Xuanling St	65	0.20%	37	1.76	24.00	32,400
42011605	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区王家河街道	Wangjiahe Street	62	0.11%	42	1.48	11.61	55,203
42011606	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区木兰乡	Magnolia Township	48	0.09%	36	1.33	10.10	50,665
42011607	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区蔡家榨街道	Cai Jia Zhu Street	53	0.13%	41	1.29	25.93	39,546
42011608	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区六指街道	Six-fingered street	116	0.17%	89	1.30	9.71	67,520
42011609	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区罗汉寺街道	Luohan Temple St	65	0.09%	48	1.35	9.82	72,000
42011610	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区李家集街道	Lijiaji Street	87	0.11%	67	1.30	15.09	78,264
42011611	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区祁家湾街道	Lujian Street	117	0.14%	87	1.34	15.25	86,260
42011612	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区横店街道	Hengdian Street	143	0.25%	112	1.28	14.47	58,309
42011613	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区天河街道	Tianhe Street	35	0.13%	29	1.21	16.36	27,376
42011614	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区滠口街道	Huangkou Streets	122	0.19%	88	1.39	12.57	62,840
42011615	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区武湖街道	Wuhu Street	124	0.30%	88	1.41	10.09	41,380
42011616	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区三里桥街道	Sanliqiao Street	26	0.14%	19	1.37	10.00	18,457
42011618	Huangpi	湖北省武汉市黄陂区武汉盘龙	Panlong City EDZ	491	1.07%	326	1.51	12.39	45,795
42011701	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区郑城街道	Xinzhou Streets	238	0.14%	175	1.36	10.00	170,451
42011703	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区辛冲街道	Xin Chong Street	71	0.12%	39	1.82	22.76	57,377
42011704	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区旧街街道	Old Street Street	46	0.07%	32	1.44	12.20	68,580
42011705	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区道观河管	Taoguanhe Mgmt	6	0.13%	3	2.00	22.22	4,459
42011706	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区徐古街道	Xugu Street	19	0.05%	13	1.46	10.17	37,811
42011707	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区潘塘街道	Pantang Street	18	0.06%	15	1.20	0.00	29,677
42011708	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区三店街道	Three shop streets	75	0.10%	56	1.34	12.77	73,587
42011709	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区凤凰镇	Phoenix Town	41	0.16%	30	1.37	19.05	26,219
42011710	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区汪集街道	Wangji Street	58	0.07%	38	1.53	10.58	77,923
42011711	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区李集街道	Liji Street	51	0.09%	44	1.16	4.70	55,329
42011712	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区仓埠街道	Cangbu Street	89	0.11%	63	1.41	15.47	80,619
42011713	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区阳逻街道	Yanglu Street	332	0.22%	233	1.42	12.52	150,457
42011714	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区双柳街道	Shuangliu Street	58	0.10%	37	1.57	16.98	56,254
42011716	Xinzhou	湖北省武汉市新洲区张渡湖街道	Rising Lake Street	14	0.16%	10	1.40	2.94	8,531

全市合计的确诊病例+无症状感染者	Known Streets	51,81	28,79	1.80	
街道不详者	Unknown Streets	3	2		
街道不详、跨区跨街道等	Total	187	495	0.38	
		52,32	29,40	1.78	10,945,89
		7	5		6

Appendix E: Geospatial & Organizational Information for ~ 171 Wuhan Hospitals with Health Care Worker cases^{31 32}

District	ADM	Lat	Lon	ID	Hospital	HospitalTranslated	Rank	Type
Hongshan	42011104	30.53	114.37	1	湖北六七二中西医结合	Hubei 672 W/TCM orthopaedic H	3 A	Ortho
Wuchang	42010613	30.54	114.38	2	湖北省地质职工医院	Hubei Geological Staff H	2 B	Comm
Qiaokou	42010409	30.58	114.26	3	湖北省第三人民医院	3rd People's H of Hubei Prv	3 A	Gen
Xinzhou		30.85	114.81	4	湖北省第三人民	3rd People's H of Hubei Prv (Yanglu H)	3 A	Gen
Hongshan	42011103	30.62	114.38	5	湖北省妇幼保健院	Hubei Maternal and Child Health H	3 A	Comm
Hongshan	42011116	30.51	114.38	6	湖北省荣军医院	Rongjun H, Hubei Prv	2 A	Gen
Qiaokou	42010405	30.59	114.26	7	湖北省武汉女子监狱医院	Wuhan Women's Prison H, Hubei Prv	2 B	Comm
Jiang'an	42010210	30.60	114.31	8	湖北省武警总队医院	Hubei Provincial Armed Police HQ H	3 A	Gen
Xinzhou	42011713	30.68	114.59	9	湖北省阳逻中心医院	Yangluo Central H, Hubei Prv	2 A	Gen
Wuchang	42010612	30.55	114.35	10	湖北省直属机关医院	Hubei Prv directly under the organ H	2 A	Gen
Jianghan	42010209	30.64	114.31	11	湖北省中西医结合医院	Hubei Prv W/TCM H	3 A	Gen
Hongshan	42011102	30.51	114.42	12	湖北省中医院	Hubei Central H	3 A	TCM
Wuchang	42010611	30.56	114.32	13	湖北省中医院花园山院区	Gdn Mtn H Area, Central H, Hubei Prv	3 A	TCM
Hongshan	42011116	30.51	114.37	14	湖北省肿瘤医院	Hubei Cancer H	3 A	Onco
Qingshan	42010702	30.64	114.41	15	华润武钢总医院	China Resources Wugang General H	3 A	Gen
Hongshan	42011104	30.48	114.36	16	华中农业大学社区卫生服务中心	CHSC, Central Ag U of China	1 A	Comm
Qiaokou	42010403	30.58	114.25	17	三六〇四医院	3604 H	3 A	Gen
Wuchang	42010602	30.54	114.31	18	武汉大学人民医院	Wuhan University People's H	3 A	Gen
Jiangxia	42011518	30.45	114.45	19	武汉大学人民医院东院	Wuhan University People's H East H	3 A	Gen
Jiang'an	42010212	30.65	114.34	20	武汉岱山医院	Wuhan Lushan H	1 A	Comm
Hongshan	42011119	30.47	114.39	21	武汉东湖新技术开发区关东	E-L H-T DZ Kanto St Longcheng CHSC	1 A	Comm
Dongxihu	42011203	30.65	114.04	22	武汉东西湖区走马岭街中心卫生院	Wuhan E-W Lake Maling St CH	1 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010207	30.61	114.29	23	武汉儿童医院	Wuhan Children's H	3 A	Gen
Jiang'an	42011108	30.52	114.33	24	武汉方泰医院	Wuhan Fangtai H	2 A	Gen
Qingshan	42010709	30.62	114.48	25	武汉钢铁(集团)公司第二职工医院	WISCO 2nd staff H	3 B	Gen
Jiang'an	42010218	30.62	114.30	26	武汉弘济Orthopaedic Hospital	Wuhan Hongji Orthopaedic H	3 A	Ortho
Hongshan	42011117	30.59	114.38	27	武汉厚德康医院	Wuhan HouDekang H	2 B	Comm
Huangpi	42011616	30.77	114.44	28	武汉黄陂三里桥街道卫生院	Wuhan Huangxuan Sanliqiao St HH	1 A	Comm
Huangpi	42011601	30.62	114.31	29	武汉黄浦中西医结合妇产医院	Wuhan Huangpu W/TCM maternity	2 A	Gen
Caidian	42011401	30.58	114.04	30	武汉济和医院	Wuhan Jihe H	2 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010311	30.62	114.27	31	武汉济民老年医院	Wuhan Jimin H for the Elderly	2 A	Comm
Jiang'an	42010212	30.65	114.34	32	武汉江岸区丹水池街社区卫生服务中心	Danshui Pool St CHSC, Riverside	1 A	Comm
Wuchang	42010602	30.53	114.33	33	武汉科技大学附属天佑医院	Tianyou H aff w/Wuhan U S&T	3 A	Gen

³¹ Maohui Feng et al, "Geographical and Epidemiological Characteristics of 3,487 Confirmed Cases With COVID-19 Among Healthcare Workers in China", *Frontiers in Public Health* (1/26/2021).

<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpubh.2020.586736/full>

³² Peixiao Wang, "Spatiotemporal Differences of COVID-19 Infection Among Healthcare Workers and Patients in China From January to March 2020 ", *IEEE Access* (2/9/2021).

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349182257_Spatiotemporal_Differences_of_COVID-19_Infection_Among_Healthcare_Workers_and_Patients_in_China_From_January_to_March_2020

Wuchang	42011107	30.59	114.39	34	武汉梨园医院	Wuhan Pear Garden H	3 A	Gen
Qiaokou	42010415	30.57	114.27	35	武汉普爱医院	Wuhan Puai H	3 A	Gen
Qiaokou	42010403	30.58	114.25	36	武汉仁爱医院	Wuhan Renai H	2 A	Gen
Jianghan	42010307	30.57	114.30	37	武汉商职医院	Wuhan Commercial H	2 A	Comm
Caidian	42011406	30.52	114.10	38	武汉市蔡甸区大集街卫生院	Daji St Health H in Caidian	1 A	Comm
Caidian	42011411	30.57	114.05	39	武汉市蔡甸区人民医院	Caidian People's H,	2 A	Gen
Caidian	42011407	30.48	113.93	40	武汉市蔡甸区永安街朴树村卫生室	Park Tree Village HR on Yong'an St	1 A	Comm
Caidian	42011409	30.48	113.99	41	武汉市蔡甸区寥山街卫生院常福分院	Changfu Branch of Lushan St HH	B	Comm
Caidian	42011405	30.58	114.03	42	武汉市蔡甸区TCM Hospital	Medicine H in Caidian	2 A	Gen
Caidian	42011402	30.48	113.83	43	武汉市蔡甸区侏儒街卫生院	Dwarf St Health H in Caidian	1 A	Comm
Jiang'an	42010208	30.61	114.31	44	武汉市第八医院	Wuhan 8th H	2 A	Gen
Qingshan	42010710	30.63	114.37	45	武汉市第九医院	Wuhan 9th H	2 A	Gen
Jiang'an	42010207	30.61	114.30	46	武汉市第六医院	Wuhan 6th H	3 B	Gen
Wuchang	42010612	30.55	114.34	47	武汉市第七医院	Wuhan 7th H	2 A	Gen
Wuchang	42010603	30.55	114.31	48	武汉市第三医院	Wuhan 3rd H	3 A	Gen
Hongshan	42011102	30.50	114.42	49	武汉市第三医院 (光谷院区)	Wuhan 3rd H (Guanggu H)	3 A	Gen
Qiaokou	42010415	30.57	114.27	50	武汉市第四医院	Wuhan 4th H	3 A	Gen
Hanyang	42010507	30.55	114.28	51	武汉市第五医院	Wuhan 5th H	3 A	Gen
Jianghan	42010306	30.60	114.27	52	武汉市第一口腔医院	Wuhan 1st Oral H	3 B	Oral
Qiaokou	42010406	30.60	114.20	53	武汉市第一医院	Wuhan 1st H	3 A	Gen
Hongshan	42011114	30.54	114.53	54	武汉市东湖高新区花山街社	Huashan St CHSC, EL H-T	1 A	Comm
Wuchang	42011117	30.56	114.42	55	武汉市东湖生态旅游风景区	2nd CHSC of EL Ecotourism SA	1 A	Comm
Hongshan	42011112	30.52	114.38	56	武汉市东湖新技术开发区佛祖岭社	EL H-T DZ Buddha Zuling CSC	1 A	Comm
Hongshan	42011114	30.54	114.53	57	武汉市东湖新技术开发区花	Huashan St CHSC, East Lake H-T DZ,	1 A	Comm
Hongshan	42011112	30.50	114.43	58	武汉市东湖新技术开发区左岭	Zuoling St HSC, East Lake H-T DZ	1 A	Comm
Dongxihu	42011210	30.73	114.13	59	武汉市东西湖区柏泉街卫生院	ParkQuan St Health H, E-W L	1 A	Comm
Dongxihu	42011214	30.66	114.26	60	武汉市东西湖区第二人民医院	2nd People's H of E-W L	2 A	Gen
Dongxihu	42011212	30.68	114.18	61	武汉市东西湖区金银湖街卫生院	Jinyin Lake St Health H in E-W L	1 A	Comm
Dongxihu	42011211	30.63	114.14	62	武汉市东西湖区泾河街卫生院	Weihe St Health H in E-W L	1 A	Comm
Dongxihu	42011215	30.68	114.17	63	武汉市东西湖区径河街卫生院	Wuhan E-W LTrail River St HH	1 A	Comm
Dongxihu	42011212	30.66	114.14	64	武汉市东西湖区人民医院	Wuhan East-West Lake People's H	3 B	Gen
Dongxihu	42011208	30.66	114.26	65	武汉市东西湖区辛安渡街卫生院	Xin'andu St Health H, E-W L	1 A	Comm
Dongxihu	42011201	30.62	114.14	66	武汉市东西湖区长青街卫生院	Changqing St Health H, E-W L	1 A	Comm
Hongshan	42011110	30.59	114.43	67	武汉市肺科医院	Wuhan Lung H	3 B	ID
Hanyang	42010507	30.50	114.33	68	武汉市汉阳区万松街社区卫生服务中心	Wansong St CHSC, Hanjiang	1 A	Comm
Jiang'an	42010212	30.63	114.33	69	武汉市汉口医院	Hankou H	2 A	Gen
Hannan	42011308	30.32	114.08	70	武汉市汉南区人民医院	Hannan People's H	2 B	Gen
Hanyang	42010508	30.58	114.22	71	武汉市汉阳区二桥街社区卫生服务中心	2nd Bridge St CHSC, Hanyang	1 A	Comm
Hanyang	42010507	30.56	114.28	72	武汉市汉阳区建桥街社区卫生服务中心	Jianqiao St CHSC, Hanyang	1 A	Comm
Hanyang	42010509	30.58	114.20	73	武汉市汉阳区琴断口街社区卫生服务中心	Qinkou St CHSC, Hanyang	1 A	Comm
Hanyang	42010502	30.55	114.25	74	武汉市汉阳医院	Hanyang H	3 B	Gen
Jianghan	42010307	30.62	114.28	75	武汉市红十字会医院	Wuhan Red Cross H	2 A	Gen
Hongshan	42011102	30.51	114.42	76	武汉市洪山区关山街长动社	Changying CHSC on Guanshan St	1 A	Comm
Hongshan	42011102	30.49	114.33	77	武汉市洪山区狮子山街华中农	CHSC of Huazhong Ag. U, Lion Mtn St	1 A	Comm
Hongshan	42011103	30.53	114.37	78	武汉市洪山区王兵西医内科诊所	Wang Bingxi Medical Clinic	1 A	Comm
Hongshan	42011105	30.49	114.30	79	武汉市洪山区张家湾街光霞社区	Zhangjiawan St Guangxia CHSS	1 A	Comm
Hongshan	42011105	30.50	114.29	80	武汉市洪山区张家湾街社区	Zhangjiawan St CHSC in Hongshan	1 A	Comm
Hongshan	42011103	30.52	114.36	81	武汉市洪山区TCM Hospital	Hongshan TCM H, Wuhan	3 A	TCM
Hongshan	42011116	30.51	114.40	82	武汉市洪山区卓刀泉街卫生中心	Zhuo Daoquan St Health Center	1 A	Comm
Huangpi	42011601	30.89	114.38	83	武汉市黄陂区妇幼保健院	Women's/ Children's HH	1 A	Comm
Huangpi	42011612	30.81	114.30	84	武汉市黄陂区横店街中心卫生院	Hengdian St CHH	1 A	Comm
Huangpi	42011606	31.11	114.47	85	武汉市黄陂区木兰乡卫生院	Magnolia Township HH	1 A	Comm
Huangpi	42011601	30.87	114.39	86	武汉市黄陂区前川街道卫生院	Qianchuan St HH, Huangxuan	1 A	Comm

Huangpi	42011601	30.90	114.37	87	武汉市黄陂区前川街环城社区卫生	The CHSC of Qianchuan St Ring City	1 A	Comm
Huangpi	42011601	30.89	114.38	88	武汉市黄陂区人民医院	Huangxuan People's H,	3 B	Gen
Huangpi	42011618	30.74	114.26	89	武汉市黄陂区人民医院 (盘龙分院)	Huangxuan People's H (Panlong Br)	3 B	Gen
Huangpi	42011616	30.75	114.43	90	武汉市黄陂区三里桥街邓畈村卫生室	HR of Deng Wei Village, Sanliqiao St	1 A	Comm
Huangpi	42011613	30.89	114.38	91	武汉市黄陂区天河卫生院	Tianhe Health H, Huangxian	1 A	Comm
Huangpi	42011605	30.98	114.45	92	武汉市黄陂区王家河街道卫生院	Wangjiahe St Health H, Huangxian	1 A	Comm
Huangpi	42011603	31.26	114.39	93	武汉市黄陂区姚家集街道卫生院	Yaojiaji St Health H in Huangxian	1 A	Comm
Huangpi	42011601	30.88	114.38	94	武汉市黄陂区TCM Hospital	TCM H, HuangxianWuhan	3 A	TCM
Jianghan	42010308	30.59	114.29	95	武汉市急救中心	Wuhan Emergency Center	1 A	Comm
Jiang'an	42010218	30.65	114.32	96	武汉市江岸区百步亭花园社区	The CHSC of The Park Pavilion Gdn	1 A	Comm
Jiang'an	42010214	30.68	114.38	97	武汉市江岸区谏家矶街社区卫生服务中心	The CHSC of Yanjiaji St in Jiangjiang	1 A	Comm
Jiang'an	42010207	30.61	114.30	98	武汉市江岸区劳动街社区卫生服务中心	Labor St CHSC, Riverside	1 A	Comm
Jiang'an	42010207	30.61	114.31	99	武汉市江岸区劳动街赵家条社	Zhaojia-bin CHSS, Labor St	1 A	Comm
Jiang'an	42010211	30.60	114.30	100	武汉市江岸区球场街北区社区卫生服务中心	CHSC, NorthStadium St	1 A	Comm
Jiang'an	42010219	30.64	114.29	101	武汉市江岸区塔子湖街社区卫生服务中心	Tazihu St CHSC, Riverside	1 A	Comm
Jiang'an	42010213	30.61	114.29	102	武汉市江岸区台北街社区卫生服务中心	Taipei St CHSC, Riverside	1 A	Comm
Jiang'an	42010206	30.60	114.29	103	武汉市江岸区西马街社区卫生服务中心	Xima St CHSC, Riverside	1 A	Comm
Jiang'an	42010208	30.61	114.32	104	武汉市江岸区永清街社区卫生服务中心	Yongqing St CHSC, Jiangjiang	1 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010313	30.61	114.25	105	武汉市江汉区常青街社区卫生服务中心	Evergreen St CHSC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010313	30.64	114.27	106	武汉市江汉区汉兴街社区卫生	Chang II CHSS Hanxing St CHSC	1 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010310	30.60	114.29	107	武汉市江汉区疾病预防控制中心	CDC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010301	30.58	114.29	108	武汉市江汉区满春街社区卫生服务中心	Manchun St CHSC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010302	30.58	114.30	109	武汉市江汉区民权街社区卫生服务中心	CHSC of Civil Rights St, Jianghan	1 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010305	30.58	114.29	110	武汉市江汉区民意街社区卫生服务中心	Public Opinion St CHSC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010307	30.58	114.30	111	武汉市江汉区民族街社区卫生服务中心	CHSC of National St, Jianghan	1 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010306	30.58	114.29	112	武汉市江汉区前进街社区卫生服务中心	Forward St CHSC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010309	30.59	114.28	113	武汉市江汉区万松街社区卫生服务中心	Wansong St CHSC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010309	30.59	114.27	114	武汉市江汉区万松街社区卫生中心	Wansong St CHC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010308	30.59	114.29	115	武汉市江汉区新华街社区卫生服务中心	Xinhua St CHSC, Jianghan	1 A	Comm
Jiangxia	42011513	30.41	114.31	116	武汉市江夏经济开发区大桥新区	CHSC Bridge New Area, Jiangxia EDZ	1 A	Comm
Jiangxia	42011517	30.41	114.42	117	武汉市江夏区藏龙岛社区卫生服务中心	Tibetan Long Island CHSC	1 A	Comm
Jiangxia	42011501	30.38	114.33	118	武汉市江夏区第一人民医院	First People's H, Jiangxia	3 A	Gen
Jiangxia	42011501	30.35	114.32	119	武汉市江夏区妇幼保健院	Women's/Children's HH	1 A	Comm
Jiangxia	42011501	30.38	114.33	120	武汉市江夏区疾病预防控制中心	CDC, Jiangxia	1 A	Comm
Jiangxia	42011504	30.25	114.34	121	武汉市江夏区乌龙泉卫生院	Health H, Jiangxia	1 A	Comm
Jiangxia	42011504	30.26	114.35	122	武汉市江夏区乌龙泉卫生院土地堂分院	Wulongquan HH Land Branch	B	Comm
Jiangxia	42011501	30.35	114.32	123	武汉市江夏区纸坊卫生院	Paper House Health H	1 A	Comm
Jiangxia	42011504	30.35	114.32	124	武汉市江夏区TCM Hospital	TCM H in Jiangxia	2 A	TCM
Dongxihu	42011214	30.67	114.29	125	武汉市金银潭医院	Jinyintan H	3 A	ID
Caidian	42011409	30.41	114.10	126	武汉市经济开发区军山街卫生院	Military Hill St Health H, Wuhan EDZ	1 A	Comm
Jiang'an	42010209	30.63	114.32	127	武汉市精神卫生中心	Wuhan Mental Health Center	3 A	Psych
Wuchang	42011107	30.62	114.40	128	武汉市梨园社区卫生服务中心	Pear Garden CHSC,	1 A	Comm
Qingshan	42010701	30.64	114.33	129	武汉市普仁江岸医院	Puren RiverBank H,	2 A	Gen
Qingshan	42010701	30.64	114.39	130	武汉市普仁医院	Puren H,	3 A	Gen
Qiaokou	42010405	30.58	114.27	131	武汉市硚口区宝丰街社区卫生服务中心	Baofeng St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm
Qiaokou	42010416	30.59	114.22	132	武汉市硚口区古田街社区卫生服务中心	Gutian St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm
Qiaokou	42010403	30.59	114.22	133	武汉市硚口区韩家墩街社区卫生服务中心	Han Jiakuan St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm
Qiaokou	42010404	30.58	114.25	134	武汉市硚口区汉水桥街社区卫生服务中心	Hanshuiqiao St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm
Qiaokou	42010409	30.57	114.27	135	武汉市硚口区汉中南街社区卫生服务中心	Hanzhong St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm
Qiaokou	42010406	30.58	114.26	136	武汉市硚口区荣华街社区卫生服务中心	Ronghua St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm
Qiaokou	42010414	30.58	114.27	137	武汉市硚口区长风街社区服务中心	Changfeng St CSS, Lukou	1 A	Comm
Qiaokou	42010403	30.59	114.23	138	武汉市硚口区宗关街社区卫生服务中心	Zongguan St CHSC, Lukou	1 A	Comm
Qingshan	42010707	30.62	114.44	139	武汉市青山区厂前街社区卫生服务中心	Qingshan Factory Front St CHSC	1 A	Comm

Qingshan	42010704	30.64	114.41	140	武汉市青山区红钢城街社区卫生服务中心	Red Steel City St CHSC in Qingshan	1 A	Comm
Qingshan	42010703	30.64	114.40	141	武汉市青山区新沟桥街社区卫生服务中心	Xingouqiao St CHSC, Qingshan	1 A	Comm
Wuchang	42010601	30.53	114.30	142	白沙洲街社区卫生服务中心	Baishazhou St CHSC, Wuchang	1 A	Comm
Wuchang	42010607	30.56	114.31	143	武汉市武昌区积玉桥街社区卫生服务中心	Yujiao St CHSC, Wuchang	1 A	Comm
Wuchang	42010603	30.55	114.32	144	武汉市武昌区疾病预防控制中心	Wuchang CDC, Wuhan	1 A	Comm
Wuchang	42010603	30.54	114.32	145	武汉市武昌区首义路街社区卫生服务中心	WuchangWuhan, First Yilu St CHSC	1 A	Comm
Wuchang	42010610	30.61	114.35	146	武汉市武昌区杨园街第二社区	2nd CHSC on Yangyuan St	1 A	Comm
Wuchang	42010610	30.61	114.36	147	武汉市武昌区杨园街武汉理工大学社	Wuhan U S&T CHSC, Yangyuan St	1 A	Comm
Wuchang	42010611	30.54	114.34	148	武汉市武昌区中南路街南湖	South Lake CHSC, Zhongnan Road St	1 A	Comm
Wuchang	42010610	30.61	114.35	149	武汉市武昌医院	Wuchang H,	3 A	Gen
Wuchang	42010708	30.58	114.47	150	武汉市武东医院	Wudong H,	2 A	Psych
Xinzhou	42011701	30.85	114.81	151	武汉市新洲区人民医院	People's H of Xinzhou	2 A	Gen
Xinzhou	42011713	30.67	114.58	152	武汉市新洲区阳逻社区卫生服务中心	Yanglu CHSC, Xinzhou Wuhan	1 A	Comm
Xinzhou	42011701	30.86	114.81	153	武汉市新洲区TCM Hospital	TCM H, Xinzhou Wuhan	2 A	TCM
Xinzhou	42011701	30.85	114.81	154	武汉市新洲区邾城卫生服务中心	Wuhan Xinzhou Lucheng HSC	1 A	Comm
Jianghan	42010311	30.62	114.27	155	武汉市优抚医院	Wuhan Yufu H	2 A	Gen
Jiang'an	42010202	30.59	114.30	156	武汉市中心医院	Center H	3 A	Gen
Jianghan	42010311	30.63	114.27	157	武汉市中心医院后湖院区	Center H Back Lake H	3 A	Gen
Jiang'an	42010203	30.59	114.30	158	武汉市TCM Hospital	Wuhan TCM H	3 A	TCM
Dongxihu	42011217	30.64	114.16	159	武汉太康医院	Wuhan Taikang H	2 A	Gen
Qiaokou	42010405	30.59	114.27	160	武汉同济医院	Wuhan Tongji H	3 A	Gen
Wuchang	42010613	30.54	114.34	161	武汉武钢医院	Wuhan Wupan H	2 B	Gen
Jianghan	42010308	30.59	114.28	162	武汉协和医院	Wuhan Concord H [Union]	3 A	Gen
Caidian	42011401	30.56	114.14	163	武汉新天医院	Wuhan Xintian H	2 B	Comm
Hanyang	42010511	30.51	114.21	164	武汉亚心总医院	Wuhan Yaxin General H	3 A	Gen
Jianghan	42010306	30.59	114.29	165	武汉亚洲心脏病医院	Wuhan Asian Heart H	3 A	Heart
Hongshan	42011102	30.51	114.42	166	武汉长动医院	Wuhan Changying H	2 A	Gen
Wuchang	42010612	30.56	114.36	167	武汉中南医院	Wuhan Zhongnan H	3 A	Gen
Wuchang	42010609	30.59	114.33	168	武汉紫荆医院	Wuhan Bauhinia H	3 A	Gen
Jiang'an	42010213	30.61	114.29	169	长江航运总医院	Yangtze River Shipping General H	3 B	Gen
Jiang'an	42010217	30.62	114.29	170	长江水利委员会长江医院	Yangtze River Water Res Comm H	2 B	Comm
Hongshan	42011104	30.51	114.36	171	中建三局武汉中心医院	China Const Bureau Wuhan Central H	2 B	Gen
Dongxihu					Wuhan Golden & Silver Lake Hospital	Wuhan Golden & Silver Lake H		
Xinzhou					WuhanNew Island邾城卫生服务中心	WuhanNew Island邾城卫生服务中 武汉济民老年医院		

Appendix F: Authorship Demographics for the Main 38 & 65 Epidemiological Analyses

All 65 Epidemiological Studies/Sources Compiled for this Analysis - The 38 Unique Sources for the Main list are highlighted in [Purple]

Wuhan COVID-19 Outbreak - Case & Death Data Source		Country & Author Background information			
	Study [with active link]	Country	City/Prv	District	Hospital/Org
1	[protected; pending publication]	China	Wuhan		
2	1-year outcomes in hospital survivors with COVID-19: a longitudinal cohort study³³	China	Wuhan	Dongxihu	Jinyintan
3	A comparative analysis of clinical characteristics in patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 between Wuhan and Zhoushan, China³⁴	China	Zhoushan		
4	A cross-sectional comparison of epidemiological and clinical features of patients with coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in Wuhan and outside Wuhan, China³⁵	China+	Guangzhou		
5	An Advanced Study of Urban Emergency Medical Equipment Logistics Distribution for Different Levels of Urgency Demand³⁶	China	Xi'an		
6	Analysis of 92 deceased patients with COVID-19	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Renmin
7	Analysis of clinical characteristics and laboratory findings of 95 cases of 2019 novel coronavirus pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a retrospective analysis³⁷	China	Wuhan	Xinzhou	People's Hospital
8	Analysis of clinical features of COVID-19 in cancer patients³⁸	China	Wuhan	Qiaokou	Wuhan No. 1
9	Analysis of the Risk Factors for Mortality in Adult COVID-19 Patients in Wuhan: A Multicenter Study³⁹	China	Wuhan	Wuchang+	Zhongnan+
10	Association of D-dimer elevation with inflammation and organ dysfunction in ICU patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a retrospective observational study⁴⁰	China	Wuhan+	Dongxihu	Jinyintan
11	Benefits from Shortening Viral Shedding by Traditional Chinese Medicine Treatment for Moderate COVID-19: An Observational Study	China	Wuhan	Jiangxia	Fangcang
12	Case analysis of novel coronavirus pneumonia in the Second Hospital of Wuhan Iron and Steel Company, Qingshan District, Wuhan, China⁴¹	China	Tianjin		
13	Characteristics of 1738 Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan	Dongxihu	Fangcang

³³ Lixue Huang *et al*, "1-year outcomes in hospital survivors with COVID-19: a longitudinal cohort study", *The Lancet* (8/28/2021). [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(21\)01755-4/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(21)01755-4/fulltext)

³⁴ Haifeng Li *et al*, "A comparative analysis of clinical characteristics in patients infected with severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) between Wuhan and Zhoushan, China", *Annals of Palliative Medicine* (12/31/2021). <https://apm.amegroups.com/article/view/86596/html>

³⁵ Ziyang Lei *et al*, "A cross-sectional comparison of epidemiological and clinical features of patients with coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in Wuhan and outside Wuhan, China", *Travel Medicine & Infectious Disease* (6/1/2020). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1477893920301320?via%3Dihub>

³⁶ Yongqiang Zhao & Liwei Zhang, "An Advanced Study of Urban Emergency Medical Equipment Logistics Distribution for Different Levels of Urgency Demand", *International Journal of Environmental Research & Public Health* (9/7/2022). <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/19/18/11264>

³⁷ Gemin Zhang *et al*, "Analysis of clinical characteristics and laboratory findings of 95 cases of 2019 novel coronavirus pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a retrospective analysis", *Respiratory Research* (3/26/2020). <https://respiratory-research.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12931-020-01338-8>

³⁸ Wei-Ting Cheng *et al*, "Analysis of clinical features of COVID-19 in cancer patients", *Medical Oncology* (8/28/2020). <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/0284186X.2020.1810313>

³⁹ Man Li *et al*, "Analysis of the Risk Factors for Mortality in Adult COVID-19 Patients in Wuhan: A Multicenter Study", *Frontiers in Medicine* (8/25/2020). <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmed.2020.00545/full>

⁴⁰ Wang Zheng *et al*, "Association of D-dimer elevation with inflammation and organ dysfunction in ICU patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a retrospective observational study", *Aging* (2/11/2021). <https://www.aging-us.com/article/202496/text>

⁴¹ Meirong Liu *et al*, "Case analysis of novel coronavirus pneumonia in the Second Hospital of Wuhan Iron and Steel Company, Qingshan District, Wuhan, China", *Annals of Palliative Medicine* (7/25/2020). <https://apm.amegroups.com/article/view/47486/html>

14	Clinical analysis of severe COVID-19 patients⁴²	China	Qinghai		
15	Clinical and Laboratory Predictors of In-hospital Mortality in Patients With Coronavirus Disease-2019: A Cohort Study in Wuhan, China⁴³	China	Wuhan	Qiaokou	Tongji Union
16	Clinical characteristics and analysis of risk factors for disease progression of COVID-19: A retrospective Cohort Study	China	Beijing		
17	Clinical characteristics and co-infections of 354 hospitalized patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a retrospective cohort study - ScienceDirect	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Renmin
18	Clinical characteristics and outcomes of COVID-19 patients with gastrointestinal symptoms admitted to Jiangnan Fangcang Shelter Hospital in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan	Qiaokou	Tongji Union
19	Clinical characteristics and prognostic factors of COVID-19 patients progression to severe: a retrospective, observational study	China	Wuhan	Qiaokou	Tongji Union
20	Clinical Characteristics of 138 Hospitalized Patients With 2019 Novel Coronavirus–Infected Pneumonia in Wuhan, China⁴⁴	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Zhongnan
21	Clinical characteristics of 141 deaths from novel coronavirus pneumonia in Wuhan Jinyintan Hospital	China	Changsha		
22	Clinical characteristics of 25 death cases with COVID-19: A retrospective review of medical records in a single medical center, Wuhan, China⁴⁵	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Renmin
23	Clinical characteristics of 30 COVID-19 patients with epilepsy: A retrospective study in Wuhan⁴⁶	China	Wuhan	Jiang'an	Wuhan Central
24	Clinical characteristics of 70 fatal patients with COVID-19⁴⁷	China	Wuhan	Qiaokou	Tongji
25	Clinical characteristics of non-ICU hospitalized patients with coronavirus disease 2019 and liver injury: A retrospective study⁴⁸	China	Fuzhou		
26	Clinical Characteristics of Nutritional Indicators in Patients with Covid-19⁴⁹	China	Hebei		
27	Clinical Features and CT Imaging Analysis of 76 Patients with Corona Virus Disease 暨南大学学报(自然科学与医学版);2020.⁵⁰	China	Lanzhou		
28	Clinical features and mortality factors of severe novel coronavirus pneumonia⁵¹	China	Wuhan	Jiangnan	Jiangnan University
29	Clinical features of 162 fatal cases of COVID-19: a multi-center retrospective study⁵²	China	Wuhan	3 Districts	5 Hospitals
30	Clinical outcomes of COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a large cohort study⁵³	China	Shanghai		

⁴² Hao Wang *et al*, "Clinical analysis of severe COVID-19 patients", *Technology & Health Care* (2/25/2022). <https://content.iospress.com/articles/technology-and-health-care/thc228021>

⁴³ Kun Wang *et al*, "Clinical and Laboratory Predictors of In-hospital Mortality in Patients With Coronavirus Disease-2019: A Cohort Study in Wuhan, China", *Clinical Infectious Diseases* (5/3/2020). <https://academic.oup.com/cid/article/71/16/2079/5828281?login=false>

⁴⁴ Dawei Wang *et al*, "Clinical Characteristics of 138 Hospitalized Patients With 2019 Novel Coronavirus–Infected Pneumonia in Wuhan, China", *JAMA* (2/7/2020). <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/fullarticle/2761044>

⁴⁵ Xun Li *et al*, "Clinical characteristics of 25 death cases with COVID-19: A retrospective review of medical records in a single medical center, Wuhan, China", *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* (4/3/2020). [https://www.ijidonline.com/article/S1201-9712\(20\)30186-7/fulltext](https://www.ijidonline.com/article/S1201-9712(20)30186-7/fulltext)

⁴⁶ Minxian Sun *et al*, "Clinical characteristics of 30 COVID-19 patients with epilepsy: A retrospective study in Wuhan", *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* (10/2/2020). [https://www.ijidonline.com/article/S1201-9712\(20\)32191-3/fulltext](https://www.ijidonline.com/article/S1201-9712(20)32191-3/fulltext)

⁴⁷ Chen Tao *et al*, "Clinical characteristics of 70 fatal patients with COVID-19", *British Medical Journal* (2/23/2020). https://www.bmj.com/sites/default/files/attachments/bmj-article/pre-pub-history/original_paper_23.2.20.pdf

⁴⁸ Hansheng Xie *et al*, "Clinical characteristics of non-ICU hospitalized patients with coronavirus disease 2019 and liver injury: A retrospective study", *Liver International* (4/2/2020). <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/liv.14449>

⁴⁹ Bo Yuan Zhang *et al*, "Clinical Characteristics of Nutritional Indicators in Patients with Covid-19 | Abstract (ijpsonline.com)", *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* (1/1/2021). <https://www.ijpsonline.com/abstract/clinical-characteristics-of-nutritional-indicators-in-patients-with-covid19-4226.html>

⁵⁰ X Li *et al*, "Clinical Features and CT Imaging Analysis of 76 Patients with Corona Virus Disease | 暨南大学学报(自然科学与医学版);2020. | CNKI_Lanzhou (bvshalud.org)", *Journal of Jinan University [Natural Science & Medicine Edition]* (12/1/2020). <https://pesquisa.bvsalud.org/global-literature-on-novel-coronavirus-2019-ncov/resource/pt/czh-86>

⁵¹ Qin Wei *et al*, "Clinical features and mortality factors of severe novel coronavirus pneumonia", *Chinese Journal of Tuberculosis & Respiratory Diseases* (8/12/2020). <https://rs.yiigle.com/CN112147202008/1211446.htm>

⁵² Xianlong Zhou *et al*, "Clinical features of 162 fatal cases of COVID-19: a multi-center retrospective study", *Emergency & Critical Care Medicine* (9/1/2022).

https://journals.lww.com/eccm/Fulltext/2022/09000/Clinical_features_of_162_fatal_cases_of_COVID_19_3.aspx

⁵³ Jiao Liu *et al*, "Clinical outcomes of COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a large cohort study", *Annals of Intensive Care* (7/31/2020). <https://annalsofintensivecare.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s13613-020-00706-3>

31	COVID-19 Is Distinct From SARS-CoV-2-Negative Community-Acquired Pneumonia ⁵⁴	China	Wuhan+	Jiangnan	Red Cross
32	COVID-19-associated coagulopathy: thromboembolism prophylaxis and poor prognosis in ICU ⁵⁵	China	Guangzhou		
33	Critically Ill Patients with Coronavirus Disease 2019 in a Designated Hospital in Wuhan ⁵⁶	China	Wuhan	Qiaokou	Tongji
34	Death from Covid-19 of 23 Health Care Workers in China ⁵⁷	China+			
35	Deep learning-based triage and analysis of lesion burden for COVID-19: a retrospective study with external validation	China	Wuhan	Qiaokou	Tongji
36	Determinants of mortality of patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a case-control study ⁵⁸	China	Shanghai		
37	Development and Validation of a Prognostic Risk Score System for COVID-19 Inpatients: A Multi-Center Retrospective Study in China ⁵⁹	China+	Wuhan+	Qiaokou+	Tongji
38	Diagnosis and treatment of 471 patients with 2019 novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) ⁶⁰	China	Shanghai		
39	Elderly Male With Cardiovascular-Related Comorbidities Has a Higher Rate of Fatal Outcomes: A Retrospective Study in 602 Patients With COVID-19 ⁶¹	China	Wuhan+	Jiang'an	Hankou Hospital
40	Epidemiologic Characteristics of and Prognostic Factors for COVID-19 Among Hospitalized Patients: Updated Implications From Hubei Province, China ⁶²	China	Wuhan	Hongshan	Hubei Maternal/Child
41	Epidemiological and clinical characteristics of 99 cases of 2019 novel coronavirus pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a descriptive study ⁶³	China	Wuhan	Dongxiu	Jinyintan
42	Factors Defining the Development of Severe Illness in Patients with COVID-19: A Retrospective Study ⁶⁴	China	Beijing		
43	Follow-up results of 117 patients with novel coronavirus pneumonia after discharge from Wuhan Fangcang Hospital	China	Wuhan	Hongshan	Hubei Cancer Hospital
44	Geographical and Epidemiological Characteristics of 3,487 Confirmed Cases With COVID-19 Among Healthcare Workers in China ⁶⁵	China	Wuhan	Qiaokou+	Tongji+
45	Hospitalization and Critical Care of 109 Decedents with COVID-19 Pneumonia in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan+	3 Districts	3 Hospitals
46	Investigation of 100 SARS-CoV-2 infected families in Wuhan: Transmission patterns and follow-up	China	Multiple		
47	Neurological Implications of Non-critically Ill Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 in a Fangcang Shelter Hospital in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Zhongnan

⁵⁴ Yutian Zhou *et al*, "COVID-19 Is Distinct From SARS-CoV-2-Negative Community-Acquired Pneumonia", *Frontiers in Cellular & Infection Microbiology* (6/16/2020). <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fcimb.2020.00322/full>

⁵⁵ Runhui Zheng *et al*, "COVID-19-associated coagulopathy: thromboembolism prophylaxis and poor prognosis in ICU", *Experimental Hematology & Oncology* (2/1/2021). <https://ehonline.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s40164-021-00202-9>

⁵⁶ ZH Wang *et al*, "Critically Ill Patients with Coronavirus Disease 2019 in a Designated Hospital in Wuhan", *Risk Management & Healthcare Policy* (5/16/2020). <https://www.dovepress.com/critically-ill-patients-with-coronavirus-disease-2019-in-a-designated-peer-reviewed-fulltext-article-RMHP>

⁵⁷ Mingkun Zhan *et al*, "Death from Covid-19 of 23 Health Care Workers in China", *New England Journal of Medicine* (6/4/2020). <https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/nejmc2005696>

⁵⁸ Jian Li *et al*, "Determinants of mortality of patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a case-control study", *Annals of Palliative Medicine* (4/30/2021). <https://apm.amegroups.com/article/view/67334/html>

⁵⁹ Ye Yuan *et al*, "Development and Validation of a Prognostic Risk Score System for COVID-19 Inpatients: A Multi-Center Retrospective Study in China", *Engineering* (10/13/2020).

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2095809920303581?via%3Dihub>

⁶⁰ Kebin Cheng *et al*, "Diagnosis and treatment of 471 patients with 2019 novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19)", *Annals of Translational Medicine* (1/30/2021). <https://atm.amegroups.com/article/view/61672/html>

⁶¹ Xiao-Yong Zhan *et al*, "Elderly Male With Cardiovascular-Related Comorbidities Has a Higher Rate of Fatal Outcomes: A Retrospective Study in 602 Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019", *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine* (6/7/2021). <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fcvm.2021.680604/full>

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48	Predicting Progression of COVID-19 Infection to Prioritize Medical Resource Allocation: A Novel Triage Model Based on Patient Char. & Symptoms at Presentation ⁶⁶	China+	Wuhan+	Wuchang	Zhongnan
49	Regional Differences in Epidemiological & Clinical Characteristics, Treatment, and Clinical Outcomes of COVID-19 in Wuhan and Remote Areas of Hubei Province ⁶⁷	China+	Wuhan+	Wuchang+	Renmin+
50	Retrospective analysis of clinical features in 134 coronavirus disease 2019 cases ⁶⁸	China	Hefei		
51	Risk Factors Associated With Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome and Death in Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 Pneumonia in Wuhan, China ⁶⁹	China	Wuhan+	Dongxihu	Jinyintan
52	SARS-CoV-2 Transmission in Patients With Cancer at a Tertiary Care Hospital in Wuhan, China	China+	Wuhan	Wuchang	Zhongnan
53	Sex differences in clinical characteristics and risk factors for mortality among severe patients with COVID-19: a retrospective study ⁷⁰	China	Wuhan+	Wuchang	Renmin
54	The characteristics and death risk factors of 132 COVID-19 pneumonia patients with comorbidities: a retrospective single center analysis in Wuhan, China ⁷¹	China	Wuhan	Qiaokou	Wuhan No. 1; Hubei 3rd
55	The health & economic impact of constructing temp. field hospitals to meet the COVID-19 pandemic surge: Wuhan Leishenshan Hospital in China as a case study	China+	Wuhan	Wuchang	Zhongnan
56	The incidence, risk factors and prognosis of acute kidney injury in severe and critically ill patients with COVID-19 in mainland China: a retrospective study ⁷²	China	Guangzhou		
57	The paradoxical problem with COVID-19 ocular infection: Moderate clinical manifestation and potential infection risk	China	Wuhan+	Caidian+	Huoshenshan+
58	The worldwide COVID-19 outbreak: Advice and recommendation on radiology mgmt & infection control from makeshift hospitals in Wuhan	China	Jilin		
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61	Treatment efficacy analysis of traditional Chinese medicine for novel coronavirus pneumonia (COVID-19): an empirical study from Wuhan, Hubei Province, China ⁷⁵	China	Macao		
62	Wuchang Fangcang Shelter Hospital: Practices, Experiences, and Lessons Learned in Controlling COVID-19	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Renmin+
63	Wuhan CDC Epidemiological Data Update - 20200226 - Usage of Beds in Wuhan Hospitals	China	Wuhan		
64	Spatiotemporal characteristics and factor analysis of SARS-CoV-2 infections among healthcare workers in Wuhan, China	China	Wuhan	Wuchang	Wuhan University

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China+

Wuhan

Qiaokou

Tongji

Appendix G: *Linked Topical Bibliography*

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